

THE SCHOOL OF PUBLIC POLICY

Master of Public Policy Capstone Project

Relinquishing Control: Allowing Albertans Access to their Electronic Health
Records through NetCare

Submitted by:

Belal Chemali

Approved by Supervisor:

Dr. Ronald Kneebone on March 15, 2016

Submitted in fulfillment of the requirements of PPOL 623 and completion of the requirements
for the Master of Public Policy degree

THE SCHOOL OF PUBLIC POLICY

Acknowledgements

Thank you Dr. Kneebone for your guidance and for steering me into the direction of a 'good paper' that I'm proud of. Special thanks to Joseph Abinader and Lee Harding for your contribution during the preliminary stages. Thanks to Dr. Doreen Rabi, Greg Hallihan, and Jimena Rodriguez for your feedback, insight and fruitful discussions on the subject.

Consider this: I can go to Antarctica and get cash from an ATM without a glitch, but should I fall ill during my travels, a hospital there could not access my medical records or know what medications I am on.

—Nathan Deal

The current medical records system is this: Room after room after room in a hospital filled with paper files.

—Timothy Murphy (1751 – 1818)

...To that point, little has changed since.

THE SCHOOL OF PUBLIC POLICY

Table of Contents

Chapter 1: Background	1
What is NetCare?	4
What is a Personal Health Record (PHR)?	4
Chapter 2: What's the Problem? Arguments For & Against	9
The Benefits of PHRs	9
Assumptions	16
The Questions: Arguments Against	18
Summary of the arguments for and against adopting a PHR	22
Chapter 3: Barriers to Progress	23
1) Economic and technical constraints	23
2) Buy-in from health care providers	25
3) Fear of Low Patient Uptake	28
4) Lack of an interoperability infrastructure	30
5) The battle between privacy and right to access	31
Chapter 4: Cost-Benefit Analysis – A Limited Review	33
Objective and Methods:	36
Results	39
Chapter 5: Policy & Legal frameworks	41
Current Status	41
The Issue	42
Applicable Law	42
Policies and Guidelines	49
Analysis	53
Chapter 6: Proposed Solution Based on Kaiser's	56
The Current Health Information System is Linear	56
The Health Information System Cycle	58
A Successful Story	61
Chapter 7: Policy Recommendations	64
Year One: 2016-2017	64
Year Two: 2017-2018	65
Year Three: 2018-2019	65
Measuring Success	66
Further considerations	67
Chapter 8: Conclusion	68
Bibliography	70

THE SCHOOL OF PUBLIC POLICY

Executive Summary

Getting quick answers for a medical condition could be a hassle in Canada, but getting a complete picture of your health records can be a nightmare.

Alberta is closer than other provinces in having a unified Electronic Health Record (EHR) system that serves as a single patient record. To improve the quality of healthcare and integrate the ideal of patient-centred care and health self-management, patients need full access and co-ownership of their health records. To that end, Alberta Health Services and the provincial government intend to allow patients access to their health files through the Patient Health Record (PHR) program. However, the provincial roll-out of the PHR has faced numerous setbacks and the initial targets are far from being met.

The current health information network is a linear model where patients enter the health system and data is collected from them at the point of care. This information is shared on behalf of the individual with other health providers through NetCare. However, some information is not shared. The system, and in effect the patient's record, is disintegrated as clinicians have their own data that is not being incorporated into the provincial-electronic health record—NetCare.

Currently, only physicians and authorized custodians have immediate access to all patient EHRs through Alberta Netcare. The main contention involves reconciling transparency with privacy and disclosure—a clear order of precedent needs to be created for privacy rights or rights to accessing personal information. A policy needs to be established by Alberta Health to promote data sharing and forming a unified EHR network that will serve as a single-patient record. This policy should also allow patients immediate and full access to their records through the PHR. However, the law could limit this policy because the Health Information Act places the burden of privacy protection, and in effect ownership of the records, upon the health providers.

The proposed cyclical model creates a paradigm shift where all health care providers and patients are on the same page.

CHAPTER 1: BACKGROUND

Imagine a teenager who was just diagnosed with Lupus, a chronic disease that causes inflammation of the skin or other parts of the body. Close monitoring and treatment are vital to prevent her death. But after consulting with many doctors and specialists—along with various tests, one doctor notes that the teenager is missing all medical records prior to her diagnosis. Considering the treatment and the severity of the illness, it is important to have a holistic understanding of the teenager’s medical records before making a fatal prognosis. That’s the story of Tracy Okubo and countless others dealing with chronic illnesses.¹

The benefits of health-self management have long been explored—particularly for treating chronic illnesses.² The advantages range from improvements in health outcomes to health care savings. Self-management is when patients are actively involved in their own “treatment, symptoms and lifestyle, physical and psychological consequences inherent with living with a chronic condition.”³ The definition stress dealing with a chronic condition, which requires a person to thoroughly monitor their own health. An important share of health self-management involves prevention and health promotion, which lead to improved population health, and ultimately creates sustainability in the health care system.⁴ Even modest

¹Tracy Okubo, "Managing My Personal Health Record: My Story of Living with Lupus," *Health IT Buzz*, last modified May 13, 2013, <https://www.healthit.gov/buzz-blog/electronic-health-and-medical-records/managing-personal-health-record-story-living-lupus/>.

² Kate R. Lorig, Peter D. Mazonson, and Halsted R. Holman, "Evidence suggesting that health education for self-management in patients with chronic arthritis has sustained health benefits while reducing health care costs," *Arthritis & Rheumatism* 36, no. 4 (1993): 439-446.

³ Kate R. Lorig, and Halsted R. Holman, "Self-management education: history, definition, outcomes, and mechanisms," *Annals of behavioral medicine* 26, no. 1 (2003): 1-7.

⁴ Herbert J.C. Emery, Kenneth Fyie, Ludovic Brunel, and Daniel Dutton, "The Fiscal, social and economic dividends of feeling better and living longer," *SPP Research Paper* 6-20 (2013).

investments in population health and wellness services have been found to lead to substantial savings.⁵

But patients regulating their own health necessitates the delivery of appropriate and accurate information—especially in a world with an abundance of online ‘experts.’ Hence, it is essential to deliver the right information to patients in order to avoid cases where a patient misunderstands or exaggerates their condition as a result of overwhelming information available online.⁶ Being responsive to a person’s needs is the cornerstone of patient-centred care, and if providing the right information aligns with patient values, then the health care system must reflect that.

In June of 2014, Canadian Minister of Health Rona Ambrose requested Dr. David Naylor to lead an Advisory Panel on Healthcare Innovation with a final report called, *Unleashing Innovation: Excellent Healthcare for Canada*.⁷ While still falling under the Canada Health Act, the Panel was tasked to identify five areas of innovation that will allow Canada to reduce healthcare spending while simultaneously improving the quality of healthcare. One of the recommendations was patient engagement and empowerment, which is expected to lead to advances in patient and economic outcomes. The report points to how patients can manage their own health using digital tools like patient portals and electronic health records (EHRs).

⁵ Herbert J.C. Emery, Kenneth Fyie, Ludovic Brunel, and Daniel Dutton, "The Fiscal, social and economic dividends of feeling better and living longer," *SPP Research Paper* 6-20 (2013).

⁶ Ryen W.White, and Eric Horvitz, "Cyberchondria: studies of the escalation of medical concerns in web search," *ACM Transactions on Information Systems (TOIS)* 27, no. 4 (2009): 23.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1145/1629096.1629101>

⁷ David Naylor, F. Girard, J. Mintz, N. Fraser, T. Jenkins, and C. Power, "Unleashing Innovation: Excellent Healthcare for Canada," *Report of the Advisory Panel on Healthcare Innovation* (2015). <http://www.hc-sc.gc.ca/hcs-sss/innovation/index-eng.php>

In October of 2015, the recommendations made in the report were discussed in a symposium,⁸ which involved members of the Panel—along with prominent leaders in healthcare and policy. One of the key topics of the event was the need for rebalancing the power at the provider-patient level. The panelists agreed that there is a need for shared decision-making, which requires allowing patients full and immediate access to their health records.

The report highlighted the success of pilot projects such as Kaiser Permanente and their MyChart program in the United States, which the authors from the original study claimed it improved healthcare quality.⁹ However, custodians were not optimistic about the utility of accessibility. Custodians were reluctant about allowing ease of access to their EHRs, pointing to safety and privacy issues.¹⁰ The system could be compromised if hackers gain access to health information.¹¹ The *Naylor Report*, as well as the accompanying symposium were the source of inspiration for this project.

Custodian: the main gatekeeper of health information. A care provider or organization who securely collects, shares or uses patient health information. They include Alberta Health Services and provincial health boards, health care providers, pharmacies and pharmacists.

⁸ "Symposium to explore ways to unleash health-care innovation in Canada," University of Calgary, last modified October 26, 2015, <https://www.ucalgary.ca/utoday/issue/2015-10-26/symposium-explore-ways-unleash-health-care-innovation-canada>.

⁹ David Naylor, F. Girard, J. Mintz, N. Fraser, T. Jenkins, and C. Power, "Unleashing Innovation: Excellent Healthcare for Canada," *Report of the Advisory Panel on Healthcare Innovation* (2015). <http://www.hc-sc.gc.ca/hcs-sss/innovation/index-eng.php>.

¹⁰ Lauren Vogel, "'Blue button' access to medical records," *Canadian Medical Association Journal* 182, no. 16 (2010): E746-E746.

¹¹ Kerry Diotte, "Province's Health Records at Issue," *Daily Herald Tribune*, last modified July 9, 2009, <http://www.dailyheraldtribune.com/2009/07/09/provinces-health-records-at-issue>.

What is NetCare?

Alberta NetCare is a province-wide EHR where healthcare providers share the latest health information on their patients (Figure 1).¹² It integrates the Electronic Medical Record systems—medical and treatment information from various clinicians, along with pertinent health information from other health providers. Comprehensive information is available on personal demographics, medication, laboratory tests, diagnostic images, surgeries, allergies and up-to-date immunizations (only in Edmonton).

Figure 1. Alberta’s NetCare EHR components¹³

What is a Personal Health Record (PHR)?

Patient health records are also known as electronic patient portals, personal health portals or electronic personal health records. It is an online applications that allows patients access to

¹² “Welcome to Alberta Netcare,” *Alberta Government*, accessed January 03, 2009, <http://www.albertanetcare.ca/>.

¹³ “Netcare Learning Centre: Alberta Netcare Portal (ANP),” *Alberta Government*, accessed January 03, 2009, <http://www.albertanetcare.ca/learningcentre/Alberta-Netcare-Portal.htm>.

some or all of their EHRs through their providers. In addition, some portals allow patients to enter information about their demographics, histories or current symptoms.

As a way to foster patient-centred care and self-management, PHRs allow individuals to interact and securely communicate with health care providers,¹⁴ all while playing an active role in their own health (Figure 2).

Patients are able to renew their prescriptions, see their test results, make appointments, obtain relevant health information/advice, and update blood sugar or heart pressure

readings. The patient portal is the avenue for accessing the PHR. But for simplicity, PHRs will be used whenever online patient records are concerned and instead of using the term 'patient portals.'

Electronic Health Record (EHR): an electronic storage of patient health information such as medical information, laboratory test results, diagnostic images and reports, hospital discharges, surgeries, medication profiles, allergies and intolerances, personal demographic information and immunizations. The information is available to health care providers for improving patient care.

Alberta NetCare: a secure online tool that functions as the province's shared EHR. At the moment, Alberta NetCare does not include a patient's complete medical history available at physician clinics (EMR: electronic medical records).

Personal Health Record (PHR): It is an online applications that allows patients access to some or all of their EHRs through a patient portal providers. Some PHRs allow for patient communication with their health care providers as well as the ability to enter information. The patient is in control of their PHR, which they access through a portal system.

¹⁴ "Patient Portals and E-Views - Canada Health Infoway," *Canada Health Infoway*, accessed May 1, 2016. Infoway-Inforoute.ca. <https://www.infoway-inforoute.ca/en/solutions/consumer-e-services/patient-portals-and-e-views>.

Figure 2. Highly demanded PHR features with patients taking active roles in their interactions¹⁵

The use of PHRs has led to enhancements in clinical outcomes, patient care, patient self-management of chronic disease, patient adherence to medication, patient use of preventative services, patient-provider communication, patient

A PHR allows patients to securely access their EHR anywhere and anytime to see:

- Clinic visits
- Hospital discharge summaries
- Medication
- Personal demographics
- Laboratory results
- Diagnostic imaging reports
- Surgeries
- Allergies
- Immunizations

Patients may also be able to:

- Securely communicate with health care providers
- Request prescription refills
- Schedule or cancel appointments
- Update demographic information
- Obtain relevant health information or advice
- Update blood sugar or heart pressure readings

¹⁵ Gaby Loria, "What Makes A Great Patient Portal? Top Benefits, Features and Implementation Tips," *Software Advice*, accessed May 13, 2016, <http://www.softwareadvice.com/resources/patient-portals-top-benefits-features/>.

empowerment, and patient safety.¹⁶ The demand for PHRs has increased dramatically in recent years, especially in the U.S. (Figure 3), and is expected to become standard practice in care.¹⁷

Figure 3. The rise of PHR use in America¹⁸

In what is to follow, we will elaborate on what the problem is when it comes to PHR adoption in Alberta. It is important to understand the arguments for and against PHR before we look at what the possible barriers may be. With regards to proper allocation of resources, it is also critical to understand what the literature says about the costs and benefits of having PHRs,

¹⁶ Chandra Y. Osborn, Lindsay Satterwhite Mayberry, Shelagh A. Mulvaney, and Rachel Hess, "Patient web portals to improve diabetes outcomes: a systematic review," *Current diabetes reports* 10, no. 6 (2010): 422-435.
 James D. Ralston, Irl B. Hirsch, James Hoath, Mary Mullen, Allen Cheadle, and Harold I. Goldberg, "Web-based collaborative care for type 2 diabetes a pilot randomized trial," *Diabetes care* 32, no. 2 (2009): 234-239.
 Alberta Health Services, "Engaging the Patient in Healthcare: An Overview of Personal Health Record Systems and Implications for Alberta," *albertahealthservices.ca*, last modified 2009.
 Caroline Lubick Goldzweig, Greg Orshansky, Neil M. Paige, Ali Alexander Towfigh, David A. Haggstrom, Isomi Miake-Lye, Jessica M. Beroes, and Paul G. Shekelle, "Electronic patient portals: evidence on health outcomes, satisfaction, efficiency, and attitudes: a systematic review," *Annals of internal medicine* 159, no. 10 (2013): 677-687.

¹⁷ American Hospital Association, "Individual's Ability to Electronically Access their Hospital Medical Records, Perform Key Tasks is Growing," *Trendwatch*, July 2016, <http://www.aha.org/research/reports/tw/chartbook/2012/chart2-9.pdf>

¹⁸ American Hospital Association, "Individual's Ability to Electronically Access their Hospital Medical Records, Perform Key Tasks is Growing," *Trendwatch*, July 2016, <http://www.aha.org/research/reports/tw/chartbook/2012/chart2-9.pdf>

thus we will conduct a limited scoping review of current research. To understand the possibility of having a fully integrated EHR system with a PHR capability in Alberta, we will assess the policy and legal frameworks that govern health information sharing. We will then look at successful solutions from abroad to see what may work in Alberta. Finally, we will lay out the policy recommendations for implementing an integrated EHR network and developing a PHR system in Alberta.

Patient-centred care requires providers to think of patients as partners in health. As we move closer to a new year of groundbreaking initiatives in health care, Alberta should be at the forefront in patient-centred health, which is based on holistic, collaborative and responsive care.¹⁹ A single patient record that is accessible through a PHR system is the first step.

¹⁹ Souraya Sidani, Mary van Soeren, Christina Hurlock-Chorostecki, Scott Reeves, Mary Fox, and Laura Collins, "Health professionals' and patients' perceptions of patient-centered care: a comparison," *European Journal for Person Centered Healthcare* (2016).

CHAPTER 2: WHAT'S THE PROBLEM? ARGUMENTS FOR & AGAINST

The Benefits of PHRs

There is a large body of literature describing and evaluating the PHR system at Kaiser Permanente, an integrated health delivery organization in United States. They have had tremendous success with their PHR platform for over a decade of operation.²⁰ Kaiser Permanente have developed an OpenNotes initiative that allows patients to view their doctor's notes through the PHR.²¹ The success of OpenNotes has not only shown physician and patient satisfaction,²² but American healthcare leaders view it as a worthwhile investment—injecting \$10 million in recent funding to expand the pilot project.²³

According to Partnership for Patients, when physicians are more accountable to their patient's health, medical errors are reduced and patient safety is improved—leading to savings in healthcare costs.²⁴ Savings are expected to be seen with less redundant testing, reduced visits and more efficient care. Efficiencies in surgeries were found in post-operative care where

²⁰ Terese Otte-Trojel, Thomas G. Rundall, Antoinette de Bont, Joris van de Klundert, and Mary E. Reed, "The organizational dynamics enabling patient portal impacts upon organizational performance and patient health: a qualitative study of Kaiser Permanente," *BMC health services research* 15, no. 1 (2015): 1.

²¹ Kim M. Nazi, Carolyn L. Turvey, Dawn M. Klein, Timothy P. Hogan, and Susan S. Woods, "VA OpenNotes: exploring the experiences of early patient adopters with access to clinical notes," *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association*, (2014): amiajnl-2014.

²² Tom Delbanco, Jan Walker, Sigall K. Bell, Jonathan D. Darer, Joann G. Elmore, Nadine Farag, Henry J. Feldman et al. "Inviting patients to read their doctors' notes: a quasi-experimental study and a look ahead," *Annals of internal medicine* 157, no. 7 (2012): 461-470.

²³ Jonah Comstock, "OpenNotes will use \$10 million infusion for improved website, patient advocate outreach," *MobiHealthNews*, December 16, 2015, <http://mobihealthnews.com/content/opennotes-will-use-10-million-infusion-improved-website-patient-advocate-outreach>

²⁴ Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality Partnership for Patients, "Interim Update on 2013 Annual Hospital-Acquired Condition Rate and Estimates of Cost Savings and Deaths Averted From 2010 to 2013," accessed May 13, 2016, <http://www.ahrq.gov/professionals/quality-patient-safety/pfp/interimhacrate2013.html>

monitoring saved time and accurately allowed providers to focus on patients who were in greater need of assistance.²⁵ Studies also reported positive outcomes which included: improved communication, reduced wait times, enhanced medication adherence and better use of the physician's time²⁶—all of which lead to healthcare savings.²⁷ One clinic noted that before visits, 92 per-cent of their patients had already completed initial paperwork online, which meant that the clinic saved approximately \$11,300 in new patient paperwork in one year.²⁸

The outcomes of PHRs have been reported benefit both patients and their health providers.²⁹ With full integration with EMRs, PHRs have reduced time spent on phone correspondences, and the ability to compile data electronically has been deemed much faster than with paper records.³⁰ Furthermore, the addition of the secure messaging option has allowed for the improvement of patient-physician communication. The availability of results and histories lead to productive discussions that could potentially allow the patient to fully

²⁵ Kristy Kummerow Broman, Omobolanle O. Oyefule, Sharon E. Phillips, Rebecca B. Baucom, Michael D. Holzman, Kenneth W. Sharp, Richard A. Pierce, William H. Nealon, and Benjamin K. Poulouse, "Postoperative care using a secure online patient portal: changing the (inter) face of general surgery," *Journal of the American College of Surgeons* 221, no. 6 (2015): 1057-1066.

²⁶ Saul N. Weingart, Alexander Carbo, Anjala Tess, Laurel Chiappetta, Sherri Tutkus, Laurinda Morway, Maria Toth, Roger B. Davis, Russell S. Phillips, and David W. Bates, "Using a patient internet portal to prevent adverse drug events: a randomized, controlled trial," *Journal of patient safety* 9, no. 3 (2013): 169-175

²⁷ Jennifer Prestigiacomo, "Patient Portals Can Produce Real Savings," *HealthCare Informatics*, April 1, 2011, <http://www.healthcare-informatics.com/blogs/jprestigiacomo/patient-portals-can-produce-real-savings>

²⁸ Ibid.

²⁹ Chandra Y. Osborn, Lindsay Satterwhite Mayberry, Shelagh A. Mulvaney, and Rachel Hess, "Patient web portals to improve diabetes outcomes: a systematic review," *Current diabetes reports* 10, no. 6 (2010): 422-435.

James D. Ralston, Irl B. Hirsch, James Hoath, Mary Mullen, Allen Cheadle, and Harold I. Goldberg, "Web-based collaborative care for type 2 diabetes a pilot randomized trial," *Diabetes care* 32, no. 2 (2009): 234-239.

Alberta Health Services, "Engaging the Patient in Healthcare: An Overview of Personal Health Record Systems and Implications for Alberta," *White Paper*, 2009.

Caroline Lubick Goldzweig, Greg Orshansky, Neil M. Paige, Ali Alexander Towfigh, David A. Haggstrom, Isomi Miake-Lye, Jessica M. Beroes, and Paul G. Shekelle, "Electronic patient portals: evidence on health outcomes, satisfaction, efficiency, and attitudes: a systematic review," *Annals of internal medicine* 159, no. 10 (2013): 677-687.

³⁰ E. Gardner, "Will patient portals open the door to better care?," *Health data management* 18, no. 3 (2010): 58.

understand their diagnosis, prognosis and treatment.³¹ The physician would also be able to provide the patient with the required next steps without the need for unnecessary visits. The health advice from a trusted source is vital, especially in a digital age with the existence of false information and claims online.

The PHR is also expected to have a spillover effect since it may serve as a positive externality for reducing the health care industry's environmental footprint.³² The impact of health care on the environment is rarely considered despite being a very inefficient and energy-demanding enterprise. Cost-effective carbon reduction strategies must be considered by all sectors, including health. Pollution has adverse effects on not only the environment, but also the patients, who in turn use the health care system. Negative externalities indirectly produced by the health care system include greenhouse gases, refuse, poisonous chemicals, water waste, toxic pollutants in the air and wasteful use of land.³³ The impact of ink and paper in hospitals may seem minor, but it is a step in the right direction with regards to efficiency and reducing the environmental footprint within the health sector. Going completely paperless by relying on PHRs and EHRs are ultimately expected to reduce greenhouse gases, paper consumption, transportation, plastic use for x-rays, toxic chemicals, ink and water consumption.³⁴

³¹ Clemens Scott Kruse, Katy Bolton, and Greg Freriks, "The effect of patient portals on quality outcomes and its implications to meaningful use: a systematic review," *Journal of medical Internet research* 17, no. 2 (2015): e44.

³² Marianne Turley, Catherine Porter, Terhilda Garrido, Kathy Gerwig, Scott Young, Linda Radler, and Ruth Shaber, "Use of electronic health records can improve the health care industry's environmental footprint," *Health affairs* 30, no. 5 (2011): 938-946.

³³ Ibid.

³⁴ Ibid.

Patients will also be empowered as co-partners in health,³⁵ and are more likely to support its development (Figure 4).³⁶ The paradigm trend in health seems to be a shift from a patriarchal model—doctors tell the patient what to do, to a model that empowers the patient to take responsibility for their health decisions. By taking an active role in their own health, it is hoped that there will be better commitments to medications and treatments.³⁷ Participation in prevention and health promotion is simpler through a portal that is tailored to the needs of each individual.³⁸ With the patient managing their own PHR, a person has access to a single and complete record that they may share with other health providers. This ability is significant especially for those travelling and have chronic illnesses or mental health conditions to monitor—continuity of care can be preserved.³⁹

³⁵ Canada Health Infoway, "Patient Portals and E-Views - Canada Health Infoway," *Infoway-Inforoute.ca*, accessed May 13, 2016, <https://www.infoway-inforoute.ca/en/solutions/consumer-e-services/patient-portals-and-e-views>.

³⁶ Joan Neuner, Megan Fedders, Mary Caravella, Lisa Bradford, and Marilyn Schapira, "Meaningful Use and the Patient Portal Patient Enrollment, Use, and Satisfaction With Patient Portals at a Later-Adopting Center," *American Journal of Medical Quality* 30, no. 2 (2015): 105-113.

³⁷ Marianne Turley, Catherine Porter, Terhilda Garrido, Kathy Gerwig, Scott Young, Linda Radler, and Ruth Shaber, "Use of electronic health records can improve the health care industry's environmental footprint," *Health affairs* 30, no. 5 (2011): 938-946.

³⁸ Clemens Scott Kruse, Katy Bolton, and Greg Freriks, "The effect of patient portals on quality outcomes and its implications to meaningful use: a systematic review," *Journal of medical Internet research* 17, no. 2 (2015): e44.

³⁹ Burns, T., J. Catty, S. White, S. Clement, G. Ellis, I. Rees Jones, P. Lissouba, S. McLaren, D. Rose, and T. Wykes. "Continuity of care in mental health: understanding and measuring a complex phenomenon." *Psychological medicine* 39, no. 02 (2009): 313-323.

Figure 4. Patient satisfaction with PHR use⁴⁰

Investing in digital health may not only improve health and wellness for Albertans, but it could also strengthen our economy and act as a positive externality. According to Canada Health Infoway and a study by the Conference Board of Canada,⁴¹ the economic advantage accrues from the benefits to patients, health care providers/systems and the eventual return on investment for the country. Investing in e-health programs has reduced annual health care costs, the number of days patients take off work, medical/prescription errors, and inefficiencies in care.⁴² With financial savings accrued as a result of fully-integrated EHR

⁴⁰ Joan Neuner, Megan Fedders, Mary Caravella, Lisa Bradford, and Marilyn Schapira, "Meaningful Use and the Patient Portal Patient Enrollment, Use, and Satisfaction With Patient Portals at a Later-Adopting Center," *American Journal of Medical Quality* 30, no. 2 (2015): 105-113.

⁴¹ Conference Board of Canada, "Valuing Time Saved: Assessing the Impact of Patient Time Saved from the Adoption of Consumer Health Solutions," *infoway-inforoute.ca*, September 19, 2012, accessed May 13, 2016, <https://www.infoway-inforoute.ca/en/component/edocman/resources/other/504-valuing-time-saved>.

⁴² *Ibid.*

systems,⁴³ the adoption of a national PHR is expected to result in to similar efficiencies and economic benefits.

A recent pilot project in Nova Scotia showed that PHRs improved operational efficiencies and allowed for better self-management of chronic illnesses.⁴⁴ Figure 5 shows the benefits and the factors that result in better health outcomes.

Figure 5. Benefits of PHRs based on a pilot study from Nova Scotia⁴⁵

The economic benefits of EHRs are becoming commonplace and similar estimates could be made of PHRs. According to Canada Health Infoway, EHRs have created \$1.3 billion from 2006 to 2012 in savings through less adverse effects of repeated tests—\$584 million, reduced

⁴³ Aykut M. Uslu and Jürgen Stausberg, "Value of the electronic patient record: an analysis of the literature," *Journal of biomedical informatics*, 41, no. 4 (2008): 675-682.

Hadi Kharrazi, Robin Chisholm, Dean VanNasdale, and Benjamin Thompson, "Mobile personal health records: An evaluation of features and functionality," *International journal of medical informatics*, 81, no. 9 (2012): 579-593.

⁴⁴ Stylus Consulting, "Nova Scotia Personal Health Record Demonstration Project: Benefits Evaluation Report," *infoway-inforoute.ca* (2014) accessed May 13, 2016, <https://www.infoway-inforoute.ca/en/component/edocman/resources/reports/benefits-evaluation/1995-nova-scotia-personal-health-record-demonstration-project-benefits-evaluation-report>

⁴⁵ Ibid.

administrative costs—\$800 million, and other benefits.⁴⁶ Previous research by Girosi et al. in 2005 have shown yearly savings of \$800 million in the U.S. from decreased chart pull activities alone.⁴⁷ The savings can also be seen through PHR adoption in a study done by the Conference Board of Canada to assess the number of hours saved and extrapolated to economic output (more on this in Chapter 4). According to the study, on a national scale, allowing patients access to their medical records online would reduce health-related visits by 47 million per year.⁴⁸ Each year, patients would also save 70 million hours, where 20 million are estimated to be from time off work—translating into \$400 million in annual revenue from lost wages from taking time off work.⁴⁹ The remaining hours could also lead to productivity as patients maximize their utility in other parts of their personal lives.

Using the above logic, adopting an electronic record system in Alberta would similarly lead to economic benefits for our province. Our healthcare system would see a return on investment: with less patient visits, increased health quality and reduced health care burdens. The question remains whether these benefits are sufficiently large enough to justify investment, which could take away resource allocation from other opportunities (Chapter 4). While several pilot projects are being investigated in Canada, the only mature patient-portal

⁴⁶ Dan Strasbourg, “Electronic Medical Records Deliver Efficiencies, Patient Safety, Improved Communication,” *inforoute.ca*, April 22, 2013, <https://www.inforoute.ca/en/what-we-do/news-events/newsroom/2013-news-releases/859-electronic-medical-records-deliver-efficiencies-patient-safety-improved-communication>

⁴⁷ Federico Girosi, Robin C. Meili, and Richard Scoville, “Estimating the Benefit of HIT,” *Extrapolating evidence of health information technology savings and costs*. Rand Corporation, 2005, 23.

⁴⁸ Conference Board of Canada, “Valuing Time Saved: Assessing the Impact of Patient Time Saved from the Adoption of Consumer Health Solutions,” *inforoute.ca*, September 19, 2012, accessed May 13, 2016, <https://www.inforoute.ca/en/component/edocman/resources/other/504-valuing-time-saved>.

⁴⁹ *Ibid.*

system is MyChart,⁵⁰ based out of one hospital in Toronto. MyChart has shown similar successes, highlighting progress in faster treatments, greater efficiencies, better patient experiences and less overall costs.⁵¹

In summary, the benefits of adopting a PHR include:

- Increased operational efficiency in the health care system.
- Improved quality and access to care.
- Postoperative efficiency and accuracy.
- Better communication between patients and providers.
- Added reassurance to families and patient satisfaction.
- Reduced call volumes and at clinics, both to and from patients.
- Decreased workload.
- Patients are active consumers of health.
- Patients have a holistic understanding of their own health.
- Improved chronic disease management.
- Increased prevention.
- Better opportunities for health promotion.
- Adherence to treatments or prescriptions.
- Better monitoring of health conditions.
- Smaller environmental footprint.
- Improved patient safety and care.
- Enhanced clinical outcomes.
- Reduced use of the health care system with less visits to the hospital and clinics.
- Valuable data on population health and trends.
- Continuity of care.
- More transparency and better accountability in care.
- Economic benefits.

Assumptions

To appreciate the benefits of the PHR, it is essential to assume that a fully integrated EHR record from all health providers is valuable and should be fully merged into one health

⁵⁰ “Sunnybrook Health Sciences Centre expanding MyChart online services to Family Practice Patients,” *Nexj.com*, February 26, 2013, <http://www.nexj.com/2013/02/26/sunnybrook-health-sciences-centre-expanding-mychart-online-services-to-family-practice-patients/>

⁵¹ Ibid.

information system. Numerous studies have shown the benefits of EHRs in terms of quality and efficiency.⁵² There seems to have been a surge in uptake in the international health-care community who are switching from a disintegrated paper-based system to a single-electronic record. The benefits include continuity of care, reductions in health costs, a holistic view of patient health, decreased redundancy in testing, accurate prescriptions and regimens, faster diagnoses, improved internal communication between health providers, more time for patient interaction, reduced wait times, health monitoring capability, and better management of chronic illnesses.⁵³

However, despite having EHRs now fully supported by all health care providers in Canada,⁵⁴ a minority of professionals may have some reservations.⁵⁵ The greatest barriers to adoption include privacy concerns or the perceived effectiveness of the regulatory mechanisms that are in place.⁵⁶ Nonetheless, PHR support could not be achieved without an EHR that provides a single patient record.

Lastly, another assumption is that the technical barriers are minor (Chapter 2), and will be easily resolved once the policies around PHRs are established. In reality, the technical

⁵² Sharon Silow-Carroll, Jennifer N. Edwards, and Diana Rodin, "Using electronic health records to improve quality and efficiency: the experiences of leading hospitals," *Issue Brief (Commonw Fund)* 17 (2012): 1-40.

⁵³ "Benefits to Health Professionals - Alberta Netcare," *Albertanetcare.ca*, accessed May 13, 2016, <http://www.albertanetcare.ca/Benefits.htm>.

⁵⁴ Bobby Gheorghiu, and Simon Hagens, "Measuring interoperable EHR adoption and maturity: a Canadian example," *BMC medical informatics and decision making*, 16, no. 1 (2016): 1.

⁵⁵ Sukirtha Tharmalingam, Simon Hagens, and Jennifer Zelmer, "The value of connected health information: perceptions of electronic health record users in Canada," *BMC Medical Informatics and Decision Making* 16, no. 1 (2016): 1.

⁵⁶ Tamara Dinev, Valentina Albano, Heng Xu, Alessandro D'Atri, and Paul Hart, "*Individuals' Attitudes Towards Electronic Health Records: A Privacy Calculus Perspective*," In *Advances in Healthcare Informatics and Analytics*, pp. 19-50, Springer International Publishing, 2016.

challenges could prolong or even hinder further development. For the purposes of this project, technical challenges and needs will not be elaborated on in detail.

The Questions: Arguments Against

Imagine that a middle-aged person is taken to the emergency department in the morning due to a seizure episode. Previously, the person underwent radiation therapy along with other treatments. An MRI scan was done in the morning, and then a physician sees the patient to discuss the results later in the afternoon. But before the doctor spoke, the patient was talking about surviving her cancer with her family. She had seen her MRI and made an incorrect conclusion. The radiologist read the report and confirmed progression of the disease.

This story illustrates one of the unintended consequences of PHR adoption; patient portals might not be the solutions everyone necessarily wants or needs. While patient empowerment is seen as an ideal goal, the definition of what the term entails is not clear and often misunderstood,⁵⁷ especially with regards to the PHRs.⁵⁸ Some patients may not want this authority and prefer to be passive consumers of health—with complete confidence in the judgments of their provider.⁵⁹

Many organizations attempt to emulate the successes of the Kaiser Permanente model, yet other PHR systems have not been so successful. The English PHR example is HealthSpace,

⁵⁷ Robert M. Anderson, Martha M. Funnell, Patricia M. Butler, Marilyn S. Arnold, James T. Fitzgerald, and Catherine C. Feste, "Patient empowerment: results of a randomized controlled trial," *Diabetes care* 18, no. 7 (1995): 943-949.

⁵⁸ Elske Ammenwerth, Petra Schnell-Inderst, and Alexander Hoerbst, "The impact of electronic patient portals on patient care: a systematic review of controlled trials," *Journal of medical Internet research* 14, no. 6 (2012): e162
Christiane Grünloh, Åsa Cajander, and Gunilla Myreteg, "'The Record is our Work Tool!' -Physicians' Framing of a Patient Portal in Sweden." *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, (2016).

⁵⁹ Wendy Levinson, Audiey Kao, Alma Kuby, and Ronald A. Thisted, "Not all patients want to participate in decision making," *Journal of general internal medicine* 20, no. 6 (2005): 531-535.

which was abandoned in 2012.⁶⁰ It was long predicted to fail in the U.K. because the PHR was barely used, as it was mostly inaccurate and incomplete, difficult to navigate, labourious to register, and assumed to lead to privacy breaches.⁶¹ Patient uptake is not guaranteed as some studies have shown that PHR use was less likely to be used after hospital discharges.⁶² Thus there is a fear among health providers that the PHR could become more of a stranded asset.

Another cause for concern is the elderly population, as well as the racially and socio-economically-driven differences in health care use, which would become more pronounced with PHRs.⁶³ More than 40 percent of the elderly population in America do not use the internet and are significantly using PHRs less than younger groups. Similarly, certain ethnic groups were less likely to use the PHR system,⁶⁴ which could mean that creators of these PHRs do not consider cultural factors during the development stages. Lastly, internet literacy is driven by socio-economic disparities and PHR adoption could discriminate against impoverished populations who may not have access to computers or the Internet. Such disparities in use would further isolate these communities. Although these disparities are found in American populations, this digital divide could easily be projected onto isolated aboriginal communities with poor internet access in Canada.

⁶⁰ Lyn Whitfield, "Final death knell for HealthSpace," *digitalhealth.net*, last updated May 22, 2012, <http://www.digitalhealth.net/news/27670/final-death-knell-for-healthspace>

⁶¹ Trisha Greenhalgh, Susan Hinder, Katja Stramer, Tanja Bratan, and Jill Russell, "Adoption, non-adoption, and abandonment of a personal electronic health record: case study of HealthSpace," *Bmj* 341 (2010): c5814.

⁶² A. Griffin, A. Skinner, J. Thornhill, and M. Weinberger, "Patient Portals." *Applied Clinical Informatics*, 7, no. 2 (2016): 489-501.

⁶³ Nancy P. Gordon and Mark C. Hornbrook, "Differences in access to and preferences for using patient portals and other eHealth technologies based on race, ethnicity, and age: a database and survey study of seniors in a large health plan," *Journal of medical Internet research* 18, no. 3 (2016).

⁶⁴ *Ibid.*

The largest concern for opening a new avenue for health information is privacy and security risks.⁶⁵ Both patients and health care providers fear the implications that introducing a PHR would flood the EHR system with hackers.⁶⁶ The damage caused by a leak of sensitive health information—such as the treatment of a sexually transmitted infection—would be irreparable, especially if spread through social media platforms. In a scoping review, seventy-five percent of patients were found to name privacy and security as their main concern for using PHRs.⁶⁷ There are also the questions regarding the rules of granting proxies access—family members or other sources of support. Privacy is compromised if security measures are weak, yet too many rules would constrain information sharing and take away the discretionary freedom providers have when it comes to health care practice.

With increased PHR access to clinical data, clinicians question the type of information that is immediately available. As the story presented at the beginning of this chapter illustrates, direct access to all clinical information may create unintended consequences. These issues are more pronounced for neuro-oncology patients who may misinterpret highly technical reports from radiologists.⁶⁸ A physician may also worry about medical records that contain sensitive information that could potentially compromise the provider-patient relationship. The physician's decision and professional judgment may be put on trial, especially if minor mistakes

⁶⁵ Simon de Lusignan, Freda Mold, Aziz Sheikh, Azeem Majeed, Jeremy C. Wyatt, Tom Quinn, Mary Cavill et al., "Patients' online access to their electronic health records and linked online services: a systematic interpretative review," *BMJ open* 4, no. 9 (2014): e006021.

⁶⁶ Alasdair Honeyman, Benita Cox, and Brian Fisher, "Potential impacts of patient access to their electronic care records," *Journal of Innovation in Health Informatics* 13, no. 1 (2005): 55-60.

⁶⁷ N. Archer, U. Fevrier-Thomas, Cynthia Lokker, K. Ann McKibbin, and S. E. Straus, "Personal health records: a scoping review," *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association* 18, no. 4 (2011): 515-522.

⁶⁸ Jennifer E. Cahill, Mark R. Gilbert, and Terri S. Armstrong, "Personal health records as portal to the electronic medical record," *Journal of Neuro-oncology* 117, no. 1 (2014): 1-6.

in past judgment resurfaced or are purposefully inflated for litigation purposes. Clinicians could be dissuaded from supporting PHRs since they could serve as a tool for litigation scrutiny.

Moreover, as we will elaborate further in Chapter 4, savings expected from PHR adoption are predominantly speculative and not based on evidence.⁶⁹ The cost of a fully operational PHR is a very expensive commitment that has health care officials worried,⁷⁰ especially since NetCare is not fully integrated with all EHRs and medical records in the province. About 20 percent of health care providers still do not have EHRs.⁷¹ Physicians are also concerned about a potential rise in extended office visits as the patient might have more questions about portal use, history, medical jargon as well as treatments.⁷² Another cost would be from the time that is required during the implementation stages of the PHR system as health care providers would have to be properly trained on how to use the system and readjust their work flow accordingly.

⁶⁹ M. Christopher Gibbons, Renee F. Wilson, Lipika Samal, Christoph U. Lehmann, Kay Dickersin, Harold P. Lehmann, Hanan Aboumatar et al., "Impact of consumer health informatics applications," *Evidence Reports/Technology Assessments*, No. 188 (2009).

⁷⁰ Darcy Henton, "Alberta To Open Limited Health Record Online Portal Before End Of Year," *Calgary Herald*, last updated January 15, 2015, <http://calgaryherald.com/news/politics/alberta-to-open-limited-health-record-online-portal-before-end-of-year>.

Jodie Sinnema, "Electronic Health Record System Will Cost Hundreds Of Millions, But Is Vital, Government Official Says," *Edmonton Journal*, last updated Feb 4, 2016, <http://edmontonjournal.com/news/politics/electronic-health-record-system-will-cost-hundreds-of-million-but-is-vital-government-official-says>.

⁷¹ Ibid.

⁷² Clemens Scott Kruse, Katy Bolton, and Greg Freriks, "The effect of patient portals on quality outcomes and its implications to meaningful use: a systematic review," *Journal of medical Internet research* 17, no. 2 (2015): e44. Christiane Grünloh, Åsa Cajander, and Gunilla Myretteg, "'The Record is our Work Tool!' -Physicians' Framing of a Patient Portal in Sweden," *Journal of Medical Internet Research* (2016).

John D. Halamka, Kenneth D. Mandl, and Paul C. Tang, "Early experiences with personal health records," *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association* 15, no. 1 (2008): 1-7.

Summary of the arguments for and against adopting a PHR

BENEFITS	PROBLEMS
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased operational efficiency in the health care system. • Improved quality of care. • Postoperative efficiency and accuracy. • Better communication between patients and providers. • Added reassurance to families and patient satisfaction. • Reduced call volumes and at clinics, both to and from patients. • Decreased workload. • Improved clinical outcomes • Patients have an immediate and holistic understanding of their own health. • Improved chronic disease and health management. • Increased prevention. • Better opportunities for health promotion. • Adherence to treatments or prescriptions. • Better monitoring of health conditions. • Smaller environmental footprint. • Improved patient safety and care. • Enhanced clinical outcomes. • Reduced use of the health care system with less visits to the hospital and clinics. • Valuable data on population health and trends. • Continuity of care, even when travelling. • More transparency and better accountability in care. • Economic benefit. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unintentional consequences: misunderstanding health information • Potential to become a non-usable stranded asset: poor patient and provider uptake • Aggravation of the digital divide: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The elderly ○ The poor ○ The digitally illiterate ○ Remote and isolated communities • Privacy and Security risks <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Hackers and breaches ○ Leaks of sensitive health information ○ Difficult balance between threshold of regulations • Compromised provider-patient relationship • Possible litigation for past-clinical judgments with exaggerated claims. • Translation of medical jargon. • High costs of implementation and maintenance <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Monetary ○ Clinic time lost through change management ○ Disruption of work flow • Need for additional resources for full integration and interoperability

CHAPTER 3: BARRIERS TO PROGRESS

In alignment with the previously mentioned disadvantages of adopting a PHR system, there are many barriers to progress. Barriers are especially pronounced when the status quo has inertia. These barriers are either at a systemic or an individual level.

1) Economic and technical constraints

The key stakeholders involved in a PHR system are the patients, health care providers, Alberta Health Services and Alberta Health. Each patron stands to benefit from PHR adoption, however, the main concern comes to determining who should pay for implementing and maintaining such a system. Some researchers have suggested patients, the prime beneficiary, would need to pay—and they will be eager to do so.⁷³ At the moment, patients may access paper copies of their records after paying a cost-based fee; a similar fee to cover operational costs seems logical, but it could contradict current laws and regulations (Chapter 5).⁷⁴

The health care providers adopting a PHR system would also gain a competitive advantage that could essentially increase their efficiency while also creating savings for the government, which suggests they should absorb the cost. More questions are raised as

⁷³ Paul C. Tang, Joan S. Ash, David W. Bates, J. Marc Overhage, and Daniel Z. Sands, "Personal health records: definitions, benefits, and strategies for overcoming barriers to adoption," *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association* 13, no. 2 (2006): 121-126.

⁷⁴ Patrick Kirsten, "Patients and their medical records: it is time to embrace transparency," *Canadian Medical Association Journal* 186, no. 11 (2014): 811-811.

Darcy Henton, "Alberta To Open Limited Health Record Online Portal Before End Of Year," *Calgary Herald*, last updated January 15, 2015, <http://calgaryherald.com/news/politics/alberta-to-open-limited-health-record-online-portal-before-end-of-year>.

physicians could seek remuneration for taking time to respond to patients through the PHR—if there is no compensation then why should they prioritize responding when more important matters arise?⁷⁵ The lack of clarity on who should pay for this system results in further delays to PHR development.

However, there are costs associated with unifying the system and creating an accessible portal feature for individuals. These costs are high because "AHS alone operates over 1,300 different information systems that hold patient data."⁷⁶ Consolidation would mean not only an additional price tag, but also the many sunk costs of silo systems make the custodian reluctant to change. The status quo feels like a safer approach. To further exasperate the issue, the silo syndrome has long been in discussion as a problem that plagues our health care system.⁷⁷ Health professionals do not work collaboratively across regions; placing barriers between clinicians, experts, researchers and provinces. Health-care boundaries are being drawn, and redrawn, even *within* provinces.

These barriers and silos make online communication even more complicated. Great strides have been made in getting Canadian provinces integrated with the use of electronic health records (EHRs),⁷⁸ which have shown improvements in the delivery of health care.⁷⁹ EHRs

⁷⁵ Bruce E. Landon, "Keeping score under a global payment system," *New England Journal of Medicine* 366, no. 5 (2012): 393-395.

⁷⁶ Keith Gerein, "Massive Health Information Overhaul Coming To Alberta," *Edmonton Journal*, last updated April 18, 2016, <http://edmontonjournal.com/news/local-news/massive-health-information-overhaul-coming-to-alberta>.

⁷⁷ Ake Blomqvist and Colin Busby, "The Naylor Report and Health Policy: Canada Needs a New Model," *CD Howe Institute E-Brief* 240 (2016).

⁷⁸ "Jurisdictional Peer-To-Peer Networks - Canada Health Infoway," *Infoway-Inforoute.Ca*, accessed May 13, 2016, <https://www.infoway-inforoute.ca/en/communities/pan-canadian-clinician-peer-network/jurisdictional-peer-to-peer-networks>.

⁷⁹ "Experiences of Clinicians Adopting Health ICTs In Canada - Canada Health Infoway," *Infoway-Inforoute.Ca*, accessed May 13, 2016, <https://www.infoway-inforoute.ca/en/communities/pan-canadian-clinician-peer-network/experiences-of-clinicians-adopting-health-icts-in-canada>.

increase efficiency in communication, as its records are accessible by any health care provider. The greatest success has come from Alberta with NetCare because of its success at uniting the province to use one EHR system.⁸⁰

Access to NetCare is quick and simple, but it is strictly limited to authorized custodians—who must bypass up to 21 different levels of permission.⁸¹ Separating information according to patient care, such as the Repository database and the demographic information, has created an added security measure. With the goal of uniting the province under one system, Alberta Health is collaborating with AHS to expand NetCare in order for it to include the 20 percent of health care providers who do not have EHRs.⁸² This expansion is expected to cost hundreds of millions, yet it is seen as a critical investment as it connects the NetCare system with information gathered from both primary providers and acute care. Moreover, a unified system would be critical for PHR integration.

2) Buy-in from health care providers

This is a whole topic in itself. However, health care professionals need to be completely on board with the idea of having a patient health portal. Physicians are particularly concerned about the remuneration process of potential time spent communicating through patient health portals. Another concern is possible patient misunderstandings of medical information—

⁸⁰ "Alberta Netcare Portal Links Circle Of Care For Alberta Patients - Canada Health Infoway," *Infoway-Inforoute.Ca*, accessed May 13, 2016, <https://www.infoway-inforoute.ca/en/209-what-we-do/digital-health-and-you/stories/94-alberta-netcare-portal-links-circle-of-care-for-alberta-patients>.

⁸¹ Ibid.

⁸² Jodie Sinnema, "Electronic Health Record System Will Cost Hundreds Of Millions, But Is Vital, Government Official Says," *Edmonton Journal*, last updated Feb 4, 2016, <http://edmontonjournal.com/news/politics/electronic-health-record-system-will-cost-hundreds-of-million-but-is-vital-government-official-says>.

especially in our online world that is flooded with medical information that is 50% inaccurate.⁸³ Legal risks may arise from assumptive errors before test results are returned; physicians may also be held responsible for when a patient inputs incorrect information.

Professional resistance has been the greatest hindrance in other jurisdictions just as much as in Canada.⁸⁴ The main anxieties are around increased work load and privacy concerns (discussed later).⁸⁵ Research has shown that such fears may discourage health care professionals from embracing the technology, and that for a patient portal to reach its full potential, patients and physicians need to see it as a technology that adds value to health care.⁸⁶ A surprisingly large resistance was observed within health professionals in Sweden when PHRs were first being introduced in 2012—mainly due to changes to their work environment.⁸⁷ A survey conducted in 2013 showed that there was 82% opposition to a PHR. Four main themes were identified (Figure 6).⁸⁸

⁸³ Jalees Rehman, "Accuracy Of Medical Information On The Internet," *Scientific American*, last updated August 2, 2012, <http://blogs.scientificamerican.com/guest-blog/accuracy-of-medical-information-on-the-internet/>.

⁸⁴ Simon de Lusignan, Freda Mold, Aziz Sheikh, Azeem Majeed, Jeremy C. Wyatt, Tom Quinn, Mary Cavill et al., "Patients' online access to their electronic health records and linked online services: a systematic interpretative review," *BMJ open* 4, no. 9 (2014): e006021.

⁸⁵ Ibid.

⁸⁶ David P. Miller Jr, Celine Latulipe, Kathryn A. Melius, Sara A. Quandt, and Thomas A. Arcury, "Primary Care Providers' Views of Patient Portals: Interview Study of Perceived Benefits and Consequences," *Journal of medical Internet research* 18, no. 1 (2016).

⁸⁷ Christiane Grünloh, Åsa Cajander, and Gunilla Myretteg, "'The Record is our Work Tool!'—Physicians' Framing of a Patient Portal in Sweden," *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, (2016).

⁸⁸ Ibid.

Common Themes of Concern

Figure 6. Themes of concern based on physician interviews in Sweden⁸⁹

- **Work tool:** physicians felt ownership over medical records as an instrument built for them. Sharing and documenting information was only to be internally done within the health care system. The medical record was a personalized tool with an internal language, while a PHR would make the medical record more of a burden than a tool as the information must be translated for the patient. Physicians are also less likely to input their ideas about suspected diseases until the results are in to avoid unnecessary anxiety.
- **Process:** expected changes of adopting a PHR would negatively disrupt work routines. With patients having immediate access, physicians are stressed since they must quickly

⁸⁹ Christiane Grünloh, Åsa Cajander, and Gunilla Myreteg, "The Record is our Work Tool!"-Physicians' Framing of a Patient Portal in Sweden," *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, (2016).

'catch up' to answer immediate questions as they arise. Normally, a delay allowed providers more time to read and explain records at the next appointment.

- **Workload:** PHRs are seen as harmful and would lead to misunderstandings, which necessitates spending more time and effort explaining information and justifying treatments. Medical records would also need to be explained with simpler terminology, which requires effort. An added IT feature in the overall infrastructure would cost more time and resources.
- **Control:** Physicians want control over the input of data and decision capacities—making sure it stays relevant and accurate. There is also concern that patients will now be monitoring and policing their physicians, holding them accountable for minor details and the log list—checking for unauthorized access. A sentiment of distrust would ensue from misunderstanding the clinician's intention for accessing the records, and the provider-patient relationship would be compromised.

3) Fear of Low Patient Uptake

The main reason for the failure of PHR initiatives such as Google Health, HealthVault or HealthSpace was the lack of patient uptake.⁹⁰ People predominantly saw these tools as useless since they did not support self-management and were difficult to work with. Poor patient uptake of PHRs could be traced back to the convenience features and ease of use; frustration

⁹⁰ Lyn Whitfield, "Final death knell for HealthSpace," *digitalhealth.net*, last updated May 22, 2012, <http://www.digitalhealth.net/news/27670/final-death-knell-for-healthspace>
Ton Spil and Richard Klein, "Personal Health Records Success: Why Google Health Failed and What Does that Mean for Microsoft HealthVault?," In *2014 47th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences*, pp. 2818-2827. IEEE, 2014.

with the PHR would discourage use (Figure 7).⁹¹ Patients were also unaware that these PHRs existed during implementation and the lack of interest stemmed from patient-provider communication—physicians did not encourage their participants to get involved. Patients will not use their PHR if the personal benefits are not perceived and there is no clear value for it as a convenient tool to better health.⁹²

The digital divide, as discussed earlier would also hinder PHR adoption. There are clear disparities that are strong predictors of uptake.⁹³ Certain populations are less likely to adopt PHRs if developers do not consider differences in health literacy, digital literacy, education, age, socio-economic circumstances and cultural circumstances.

Privacy and security concerns are always at the forefront. Health information is a very private matter and any doubt or uncertainty in the PHR system would lead to abandonment.⁹⁴ Patients are also less likely to support PHRs if they have sensitive information that they would like to keep private.⁹⁵

⁹¹ Gaby Loria, "What Makes A Great Patient Portal? Top Benefits, Features and Implementation Tips," *Software Advice*, accessed May 13, 2016, <http://www.softwareadvice.com/resources/patient-portals-top-benefits-features/>.

⁹² Paul C. Tang, Joan S. Ash, David W. Bates, J. Marc Overhage, and Daniel Z. Sands, "Personal health records: definitions, benefits, and strategies for overcoming barriers to adoption," *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association* 13, no. 2 (2006): 121-126.

⁹³ Robert Pearl, "Kaiser Permanente Northern California: current experiences with internet, mobile, and video technologies," *Health Affairs* 33, no. 2 (2014): 251-257.

Nancy P. Gordon, and Mark C. Hornbrook, "Differences in access to and preferences for using patient portals and other eHealth technologies based on race, ethnicity, and age: a database and survey study of seniors in a large health plan," *Journal of medical Internet research* 18, no. 3 (2016).

Bishnu Devkota, Joanne Salas, Sarah Sayavong, and Jeffrey F. Scherrer, "Use of an online patient portal and glucose control in primary care patients with diabetes," *Population health management* 19, no. 2 (2016): 125-131.

⁹⁴ Ton Spil and Richard Klein, "Personal Health Records Success: Why Google Health Failed and What Does that Mean for Microsoft HealthVault?," In *2014 47th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences*, pp. 2818-2827. IEEE, 2014.

⁹⁵ Dick Whiddett, Inga Hunter, Barry McDonald, Tony Norris, and John Waldon, "Consent and widespread access to personal health information for the delivery of care: a large scale telephone survey of consumers' attitudes using vignettes in New Zealand," *BMJ open* 6, no. 8 (2016): e011640.

N = 385

Figure 7. Top frustration with PHR use⁹⁶

4) Lack of an interoperability infrastructure

Interoperability is a technical term—used in health information technology, which is defined as the degree to which information can be shared between different operating systems and devices.⁹⁷ The interoperability of PHRs with a unified EHR system is critical for ensuring that all necessary data is available to the patient. Canada is doing better than many countries with near-universal availability of health information exchange.⁹⁸ However, there are many silos operating with their own EHRs and medical records and unifying all health care providers would

⁹⁶ Gaby Loria, "What Makes A Great Patient Portal? Top Benefits, Features and Implementation Tips," *Software Advice*, accessed May 13, 2016, <http://www.softwareadvice.com/resources/patient-portals-top-benefits-features/>.

⁹⁷ HIMSS Board of Directors, "Interoperability Definition and Background," *Healthcare Information and Management Systems Society* (2005), <http://www.himss.org/sites/himssorg/files/HIMSSorg/Content/files/AUXILIOHIMSSInteroperabilityDefined.pdf>.

⁹⁸ Jennifer Zelmer, Elettra Ronchi, Hannele Hyppönen, Francisco Lupiáñez-Villanueva, Cristiano Codagnone, Christian Nøhr, Ursula Huebner, Anne Fazzalari, and Julia Adler-Milstein, "International health IT benchmarking: learning from cross-country comparisons," *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association* (2016): ocw111.

be a daunting task. With a disintegrated EHR system, the PHR would need to be updated manually, which is inefficient since it may lead to errors and more work loads.⁹⁹ Moreover, there is also a need to keep internal communication between health care providers separate, which makes the infrastructure difficult to develop.

5) The battle between privacy and right to access.

There are many discussions in different fields about balancing the need for maintaining privacy rights with the right to access information held by public institutions. Sensitive health information can be threatened online and exposed to unauthorized users in many ways.¹⁰⁰ Possible vulnerabilities include accidental disclosure, internal misuse from snooping or intentional leaking, secondary users like researchers and outsider invasion.

While technology is meant to make life easier, the vulnerability of health information online is the greatest barrier to PHR adoption. Namely, the physician's obligation to maintain privacy standards interferes with the patient's rights to access (more in Chapter 5.) In Alberta, the Health Information Act allows patients greater access to their health records, and all relevant information must be released upon request.¹⁰¹ However, this same legislation also provides health-care officials with the power and duty to protect these records. They can pursue all measures to address risks to EHRs—thus the right to access is subject to exceptions.

⁹⁹ James S. Kahn, Veenu Aulakh, and Adam Bosworth, "What it takes: characteristics of the ideal personal health record," *Health affairs* 28, no. 2 (2009): 369-376.

¹⁰⁰ Alasdair Honeyman, Benita Cox, and Brian Fisher, "Potential impacts of patient access to their electronic care records," *Journal of Innovation in Health Informatics* 13, no. 1 (2005): 55-60.

¹⁰¹ Lawrence O. Gustin, "Health Information Privacy," *Cornell Law Review*, 1995, 80(3), <http://scholarship.law.cornell.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=2549&context=clr>

Health privacy laws protect these EHRs, which are to be used only under strict conditions, as seen in the ruling on the Rob Ford EHR leak.¹⁰² EHRs are well protected since the Ford case has showed that "looking at even a single health-care record of a patient not under one's care is a crime." However, some health care officials are not optimistic about incorporating a patient portal system, pointing to safety and privacy issues.¹⁰³ An individual using public internet could compromise their data and a tracking system could lodge itself into the EHR system.¹⁰⁴

Support of a PHR is dependent upon how confident health providers feel the privacy of a patient and the security of medical records are maintained.¹⁰⁵ Patients are just as concerned about the privacy and security of their health information. Without resolving privacy concerns over health information, whether from the perspective of the physician or patient, PHRs will not be supported. When patients do not feel reassured about their privacy, some may avoid sharing their personal information or even go to the extreme of intentionally fabricate their data.¹⁰⁶

¹⁰² May Warren, "Hospital Workers Convicted For Snooping Into Rob Ford's Personal Health Files," *Thestar.Com*, last updated May 6, 2016, <https://www.thestar.com/news/gta/2016/05/06/hospital-workers-convicted-for-snooping-into-rob-fords-personal-health-files.html>.

¹⁰³ Lauren Vogel, "'Blue button' access to medical records," *Canadian Medical Association Journal* 182, no. 16 (2010): E746-E746.

¹⁰⁴ Kerry Diotte, "Province's Health Records at Issue," *Daily Herald Tribune*, last modified July 9, 2009, <http://www.dailyheraldtribune.com/2009/07/09/provinces-health-records-at-issue>.

¹⁰⁵ Melinda Whetstone, and Ronald Goldsmith, "Factors influencing intention to use personal health records," *International Journal of Pharmaceutical and Healthcare Marketing*, 3, no. 1 (2009): 8-25.

¹⁰⁶ Jai-Yeol Son and Sung S. Kim, "Internet users' information privacy-protective responses: A taxonomy and a nomological model," *MIS quarterly* (2008): 503-529.

CHAPTER 4: COST-BENEFIT ANALYSIS – A LIMITED REVIEW

With increased health care costs at unsustainable rates, government bodies are more likely to endorse PHRs if cost effectiveness is clearly understood and a positive return on investment is expected.¹⁰⁷ The financial investment of a PHR system is one of the biggest hindrances to adoption with 87 percent of health care providers identifying hospital financial resources as the greatest impediment.¹⁰⁸ Investment models can guide policy makers as they work out the details of a feasible PHR program. To avoid unrealistic commitments, cost overruns and ultimately repeated delays of the PHR roll-out in Alberta,¹⁰⁹ a business case must be made that quantifies the health care savings, the public value added and the costs the province will incur.

Moreover, health economics requires an understanding of financial impacts of initiatives in order to allocate resources accordingly.¹¹⁰ Interventions based on studies with small sample sizes or little empirical support is correlated with a negative return on investment. Thus, new initiatives need to clearly present a case that the interventions or investments are worthwhile—reducing health care costs and improving efficiency.

¹⁰⁷ Siyan Baxter, Kristy Sanderson, Alison J. Venn, C. Leigh Blizzard, and Andrew J. Palmer, "The relationship between return on investment and quality of study methodology in workplace health promotion programs," *American Journal of Health Promotion* 28, no. 6 (2014): 347-363.

¹⁰⁸ Sara Urowitz, David Wiljer, Emma Apatu, Gunther Eysenbach, Claudette DeLenardo, Tamara Harth, Howard Pai, and Kevin J. Leonard, "Is Canada ready for patient accessible electronic health records? A national scan," *BMC medical informatics and decision making*, 8, no. 1 (2008): 1.

¹⁰⁹ Darcy Henton, "Alberta To Open Limited Health Record Online Portal Before End Of Year," *Calgary Herald*, last updated January 15, 2015, <http://calgaryherald.com/news/politics/alberta-to-open-limited-health-record-online-portal-before-end-of-year>.

¹¹⁰ Siyan Baxter, Kristy Sanderson, Alison J. Venn, C. Leigh Blizzard, and Andrew J. Palmer, "The relationship between return on investment and quality of study methodology in workplace health promotion programs," *American Journal of Health Promotion* 28, no. 6 (2014): 347-363.

Studies have shown cost reductions and increased efficiencies with integrated EHRs,¹¹¹ and thus similar assumptions are made with regards to PHRs. In an American estimate, with an 80 percent rate of use, PHRs are expected to create \$19 billion in annual savings.¹¹² With the technology supporting PHRs still at a young and lagging stage in Canada,¹¹³ advocates need a strong business case beyond estimates, with clear benefits in financial efficiency.¹¹⁴ The value is clear to some consumers, namely those with chronic diseases or multiple health problems, who may also be willing to pay monthly for PHR services.¹¹⁵ However, the costs and benefits need to be justified empirically.

From an investor's point of view, an uncertain market demand is cause for concern:¹¹⁶

- How can value added be quantified? Patient satisfaction, engagement and communication cannot be measured.
- Long-term return on investment is not clear. What are enduring system support costs?
- The short-term costs and benefits are vague. What costs can be avoided?
- Who should pay and what amount? What is the revenue stream?
- There is little evidence on patient demand for PHRs.
- It is not clear how and what information will be available.
- Adoption by both health care providers and patients is uncertain. How will health practitioners be reimbursed?
- In a fragmented health care system, full integration from multiple sources is difficult. Who will fund the labour costs for implementation?
- There is an absence of information on how workflow will change.

¹¹¹ Aykut M. Uslu and Jürgen Stausberg, "Value of the electronic patient record: an analysis of the literature," *Journal of biomedical informatics* 41, no. 4 (2008): 675-682.

Hadi Kharrazi, Robin Chisholm, Dean VanNasdale, and Benjamin Thompson, "Mobile personal health records: An evaluation of features and functionality," *International journal of medical informatics* 81, no. 9 (2012): 579-593.

¹¹² Ibid.

¹¹³ Conference Board of Canada, "Valuing Time Saved: Assessing the Impact of Patient Time Saved from the Adoption of Consumer Health Solutions," *infoway-inforoute.ca*, September 19, 2012, accessed May 13, 2016, <https://www.infoway-inforoute.ca/en/component/edocman/resources/other/504-valuing-time-saved>.

¹¹⁴ Paul C. Tang, Joan S. Ash, David W. Bates, J. Marc Overhage, and Daniel Z. Sands, "Personal health records: definitions, benefits, and strategies for overcoming barriers to adoption," *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association* 13, no. 2 (2006): 121-126.

¹¹⁵ N. Archer, U. Fevrier-Thomas, Cynthia Lokker, K. Ann McKibbin, and S. E. Straus, "Personal health records: a scoping review," *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association* 18, no. 4 (2011): 515-522.

¹¹⁶ Don Detmer, Meryl Bloomrosen, Brian Raymond, and Paul Tang, "Integrated personal health records: transformative tools for consumer-centric care," *BMC medical informatics and decision making* 8, no. 1 (2008): 1.

While the literature predominantly supports positive health outcomes for patient portal use, the cost-effectiveness of such an investment in the health care system is merely assumed. A possible reason for such an assumption may be due to the literature on the costs and benefits of telehealth,¹¹⁷ which can also be done through PHRs to remotely record patient data, thus saving both time and money.¹¹⁸

Another cause for the assumed savings that may result from patient portal adoption is the impact on health care workflow and operational efficiency. For instance, health care providers in the U.S. have reported saving \$0.63 from mailing lab results, \$17 for answering billing questions by phone, \$7 for scheduling appointments and 25 percent less visits post-surgery.¹¹⁹ Further savings could be extrapolated through less phone calls to or from patients, fewer faxes and fewer lab result deliveries. More efficient use of clinical time is expected—whether from collecting patient histories or from less appointments for results disclosure, and redundant transactions and tests could also be avoided with a PHR system. A complete understanding regarding the return on investment for patient portals is necessary to quantify operational efficiencies.

¹¹⁷ Raj Padwal, Finlay Aleck McAlister, Peter William Wood, Pierre Boulanger, Miriam Fradette, Scott Klarenbach, Alun L. Edwards et al., "Telemonitoring and Protocolized Case Management for Hypertensive Community-Dwelling Seniors With Diabetes: Protocol of the TECHNOMED Randomized Controlled Trial," *JMIR Research Protocols* 5, no. 2 (2016).

¹¹⁸ Neale R. Chumbler, David Haggstrom, and Jason J. Saleem, "Implementation of health information technology in Veterans Health Administration to support transformational change: telehealth and personal health records," *Medical Care* 49 (2011): S36-S42.

Harmieke van Os-Medendorp, Hendrik Koffijberg, P. C. M. Eland-de Kok, A. van der Zalm, M. S. de Bruin-Weller, S. G. M. A. Pasmans, W. J. G. Ros, H. B. Thio, M. J. Knol, and C. A. F. M. Bruijnzeel-Koomen, "E-health in caring for patients with atopic dermatitis: A randomized controlled cost-effectiveness study of internet-guided monitoring and online self-management training," *British Journal of Dermatology* 166, no. 5 (2012): 1060-1068.

¹¹⁹ E. Gardner, "Will patient portals open the door to better care?," *Health data management* 18, no. 3 (2010): 58.

However, the most predominant reason for assuming PHRs are cost-effective is due to the strong connection between PHRs, improved health outcomes and well-being, health self-management and disease prevention.¹²⁰ Prevention of disease and an improved population health could lead to savings and a more sustainable health care system.¹²¹

In a study by the University of Calgary's School of Public Policy, small economic investments in prevention and wellness initiatives were found to be linked to significant financial savings in health care.¹²² A conservative estimate of investing \$1.5 million into a preventative program—Pure North—resulted in health care savings of about \$3 million. Savings could be much larger for heavy-health care users—the elderly and those with chronic disease. Furthermore, broader socio-economic benefits could be implicated with improved labour productivity, income and well-being. However, these assumptions necessitate the need for further research into cost effectiveness and the direct connections to patient portals.

Objective and Methods:

It is important not to generalize the economic evaluation of adopting a patient portal, which necessitates a limited scoping review for more data on the cost and benefits of PHR systems. Emulating the methodology of Torre-Díez et al. (2015) in their systematic literature review of the cost-utility and cost-effectiveness of telemedicine and mobile-Health systems,¹²³ the following will be a similar review of PHR adoption—only limited in database scope. The

¹²⁰ N. Archer, U. Fevrier-Thomas, Cynthia Lokker, K. Ann McKibbin, and S. E. Straus, "Personal health records: a scoping review," *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association* 18, no. 4 (2011): 515-522.

¹²¹ Herbert J.C. Emery, Kenneth Fyie, Ludovic Brunel, and Daniel Dutton, "The Fiscal, social and economic dividends of feeling better and living longer," *SPP Research Paper* 6-20 (2013).

¹²² Ibid.

¹²³ Isabel, de la Torre-Díez, Miguel López-Coronado, Cesar Vaca, Jesús Saez Aguado, and Carlos de Castro, "Cost-utility and cost-effectiveness studies of telemedicine, electronic, and mobile health systems in the literature: a systematic review," *Telemedicine and e-Health*, 21, no. 2 (2015): 81-85.

materials and methods used for the purpose of this literature study was a database search through PubMed. The search was done up until August 25th, 2016. Search terms and combinations such as “cost-utility” OR “cost utility” AND “patient health portal” OR “patient portal,” “cost-effectiveness” OR “cost effectiveness” AND “patient portal,” were used (Table 1).

The search sequence used was:

“Cost utility” OR “cost effective” OR “cost benefit” AND “patient health portal” OR “patient portal” OR “personal health information” OR “electronic personal health records” OR “electronic patient portal.”

Table 1. Search Strategy				
Key Words in Document Title	Search Operator	Key Words in Document Title	Search Operator	Key Words in Document Title
“cost-utility”	OR	“cost utility”	AND	“patient health portal”
“cost-effective”		“cost effective”		“patient portal”
“cost-benefit”		“cost benefit”		“personal health record”
		“personal health information”		
		“electronic personal health records”		
			“electronic patient portal”	

Initially, 703 potential articles were identified, two of which were duplicates (Figure 8).

All 701 articles were screened using both titles and abstract assessment, of which, 465 articles were excluded and 236 articles were eligible for full text review. The exclusion was based on

the key words in the title or abstract. One article was added, Kaelber and Pan (2008),¹²⁴ since it was identified as relevant from the bibliography of another article—Sarkar et al (2010).¹²⁵

FIGURE 8: Flow Diagram of PubMed articles considered in limited scoping review of PHR cost-benefit analysis.

¹²⁴ David Kaelber and Eric C. Pan. "The value of personal health record (PHR) systems," In *AMIA Annual Symposium Proceedings*, vol. 2008, p. 343, American Medical Informatics Association, 2008.

¹²⁵ Urmimala Sarkar, Andrew J. Karter, Jennifer Y. Liu, Nancy E. Adler, Robert Nguyen, Andrea Lopez, and Dean Schillinger, "The literacy divide: health literacy and the use of an internet-based patient portal in an integrated health system—results from the Diabetes Study of Northern California (DISTANCE)," *Journal of health communication* 15, no. S2 (2010): 183-196.

FIGURE 9: PubMed articles reviewed based on search for cost effectiveness of PHRs. One was added from the bibliography of articles that underwent full text readings. Total articles assessed: 702 (two duplicates removed and one added).

Results

A total of 237 articles underwent full-text review, 29 of which made the assumption that PHRs lead to cost savings, while one assumed PHR adoption on a national scale would be costly. Two articles were found as relevant for cost-benefit analysis of PHRs, one from the original list and one that was added later on (See Figure 9):

- Riippa et. al. (2015),¹²⁶ a study from Finland, which is from the initial PubMed search. A cost benefit analysis of patients with chronic illnesses using PHRs and secure messaging showed no statistical significance for cost of care. There was a slight reduction in the cost of care with PHR and secure messaging. Cost-effectiveness could be assumed over the long run when treating chronic illnesses, however, the authors caution for the need to assess long-term effects on health care costs.
- Kaelber and Pan (2008),¹²⁷ an American study, which was added from the bibliography of fully-read articles. In their assessment, PHRs were found to have a net negative value

¹²⁶ Iiris Riippa, Miika Linna, and Ilona Rönkkö, "A Patient Portal With Electronic Messaging: Controlled Before-and-After Study," *Journal of medical Internet research* 17, no. 11 (2015).

¹²⁷ David Kaelber and Eric C. Pan, "The value of personal health record (PHR) systems," In *AMIA Annual Symposium Proceedings*, vol. 2008, p. 343, American Medical Informatics Association, 2008.

during adoption and a significant net positive value through the expected health care savings over ten years. Facilities with standards of electronic health data exchange and fully interoperable systems saw an increase in surplus. Positive net value was also correlated with third-party PHRs that had business models that the allocated payments to the largest number of consumers. Provider-tethered PHRs had no surplus and were associated with negative net values.

The literature predominantly assumes PHRs are cost-effective to the health care system based on the benefits they provide such as reduced operational costs, improved clinical outcomes and decreased health-care system demand. A full analysis of costs and savings is warranted to confidently expect a return on investment for PHR adoption.

CHAPTER 5: POLICY & LEGAL FRAMEWORKS

Current Status

The PHR has been in development since 2008 with no clear direction as to what it involves and when the patient portal will be available. The Alberta Government and Alberta Health Services have built the foundation for the PHR since 2011 through MyHealth.Alberta.ca where people can view general health information and promotional material.¹²⁸ The website also states:

You'll soon be able to set up an account to build your own personal health record on MyHealth.Alberta.ca. You'll be able to track your height, weight, allergies, conditions, and more. You'll also be able to get information from the pharmacy network so you can see a list of your medicine.

However, no policies are in place for PHRs and how providers will integrated it with NetCare. Health care professionals are also demanding standards of practice and guidelines for appropriate use when it comes to online messaging, and how the remuneration process would apply to supporting patients through PHRs.¹²⁹ To fully grasp the polices for PHR implementation it is important to understand the applicable law as well as other policies and regulations.

Policy: a standard procedure with general applicability set out to accomplish certain goals. Policies guide decision making and are not legally binding, but draw on statutes and official mandates. Policies are informal and must obey existing laws, yet they can be used to drive new laws.

Law: an enforceable rule that has the purpose of creating justice and order. Laws are formal and binding.

¹²⁸ Alberta Health Services. "An Overview of Alberta's Electronic Health Record Information System." 2013. Accessed December 22, 2015. http://www.albertanetcare.ca/documents/An_Overview_of_Albertas_ERHIS.pdf. P. 12.

¹²⁹ Naomi Popeski, Caitlin McKeen, Bushra Khokhar, Alun Edwards, William A. Ghali, Peter Sargious, Debbie White, Marilynne Hebert, and Doreen M. Rabi, "Perceived barriers to and facilitators of patient-to-provider e-mail in the management of diabetes care," *Canadian journal of diabetes* 39, no. 6 (2015): 478-483.

The Issue

There is great legal contention over the precedence of either privacy rights or rights to access personal information.

Applicable Law

For the purposes of NetCare, there are several crucial provisions that are applicable in Alberta.

Privacy Act

The Privacy Act, federally passed in 1983 establishes strict rules for how government institutions may collect, use and disclose personal information of a person.¹³⁰ Refusal of access may be challenged according to section 41 of the Act and the institution would be obliged to disclose the information pursuant to sections 48 and 49.

Freedom of Information and Protection of Privacy Act (FOIPPA)

The Freedom of Information and Protection of Privacy Act (FOIPPA), RSA 2000, c F-25 is a provincial legislation that sets out ground rules for the privacy of personal information offered by public facilities such as hospitals.¹³¹ This statute overlaps with the HIA and may be confusing in cases where a physician works with the same patient yet at different clinical settings— private office or public hospitals.

Health Information Act (HIA)

In Alberta, the Health Information Act (HIA), RSA 2000, c H-5 is the legislation that health care providers must follow during the use, collection and disclosure of health information. It

¹³⁰ Privacy Act, RSC 1985, c P-21, <http://canlii.ca/t/52qlc>, retrieved on 2016-06-16.

¹³¹ Freedom of Information and Protection of Privacy Act, RSA 2000, c F-25, <http://canlii.ca/t/52kft>, retrieved on 2016-06-16.

predominantly focusses on protecting the privacy of the patient and the appropriate sharing of information to maintain confidentiality.

Purpose of the act (section 2)

(a) to establish strong and effective mechanisms to protect the privacy of individuals with respect to their health information and to protect the confidentiality of that information,

(b) to enable health information to be shared and accessed, where appropriate, to provide health services and to manage the health system,

(c) to prescribe rules for the collection, use and disclosure of health information, which are to be carried out in the most limited manner and with the highest degree of anonymity that is possible in the circumstances,

(d) to provide individuals with a right of access to health information about themselves, subject to limited and specific exceptions as set out in this Act,

(e) to provide individuals with a right to request correction or amendment of health information about themselves,

(f) to establish strong and effective remedies for contraventions of this Act, and

(g) to provide for independent reviews of decisions made by custodians under this Act and the resolution of complaints under this Act.

The HIA allows patients greater access to their records, and all health information must be released upon request.¹³² It protects individual health information and outlines how

¹³² Health Information Act, RSA 2000, c H-5, <http://canlii.ca/t/52rj4>, retrieved on 2016-06-16.

personal health records may be accessed, collected, used and disclosed.¹³³ Records can be accessed through s 7(1).

However, the HIA grants discretionary and mandatory powers to the custodian that supersede the rights to access. The custodian is authorized or required to refuse individuals access to their record based on section. 11 and 12.

Moreover, the time limit is established according to the HIA, s 12(1), “A custodian must make every reasonable effort to respond to a request under section 8(1) within 30 days after receiving the request or within any extended period under section 15.”¹³⁴ However, section 60(1) provides the custodian with power and duty to protect health records, and all measures need to be in place to address any risks to NetCare pursuant s 60(2).

1) Health Provider Access and Sharing of Information

Based on sections 24, 28, 43 and 58(2) a health care provider can access a patient’s EHR only when authorized to do so:

- As the custodian working with the patient.
- As an affiliate performing duties for the custodian. They sign an oath of confidentiality to protect information.
- To gain enough information about the patient to do their job.
- According to the expressed wish of the patient who may want their information masked.
- To access data on a “need to know” basis—in the provider’s role to support patient care. The use, collection and disclosure of information can only be done based on the role of the professional

¹³³ “Privacy and Security,” *albertanetcare.ca*, accessed June 6, 2016, <http://www.albertanetcare.ca/PatientPrivacy.htm>.

¹³⁴ Health Information Act, RSA 2000, c H-5, <http://canlii.ca/t/52rj4>, retrieved on 2016-06-16.

2) Privacy Impact Assessment (PIA)

A due diligence process used as a reassurance measure that all potential risks to privacy have been identified and addressed. According to s 64, 70 and 71, custodians must review the impact on individual privacy from the introduction of new initiatives or systems. This process is to ensure technical compliance with the Health Information Act with regards to the privacy of using health information. A PIA must be completed before a facility access to NetCare.

3) Data Sharing and Integration

The sharing of data is guided by s 56.2 and s 56.3(1):

56.2 The purpose of this Part is to enable the sharing and use, via the Alberta EHR, of prescribed health information among authorized custodians.

56.3(1) The health professional body of a regulated health professional may in writing direct the regulated health professional to make prescribed health information that is in the custody or under the control of the regulated health professional accessible to authorized custodians via the Alberta EHR in accordance with the regulations.

4) Secondary purposes

Secondary uses of health information are for the purpose of improving the system and thus include system maintenance, research, audit/budgeting, health system planning and performance analysis. This concept will become clearer in the next chapter, but for now, it suffices to say that research is important for maintaining a feedback mechanism to allow for improvements in the exchange of health information. Individually-identifying information could be used internally or for some secondary purposes.

Secondary use

26 A custodian may use non-identifying health information for any purpose.

Research

27(1)(d) *A custodian may use individually identifying health information in its custody or under its control for the following purposes: conducting research or performing*

data matching or other services to facilitate another person's research.

34(1) Subject to sections 35 to 40, a custodian may disclose individually identifying health information to a person other than the individual who is the subject of the information if the individual has consented to the disclosure. This provision is important as it applies to section 27 (2) above.

5) Patient Access

7(1) An individual has a right of access to any record containing health information about the individual that is in the custody or under the control of a custodian.

10 A custodian that has received a request for access to a record under section 8(1)
(a) must make every reasonable effort to assist the applicant and to respond to each applicant openly, accurately and completely,
(b) must create a record for an applicant if
(i) the record can be created from information that is in electronic form and is in the custody or under the control of the custodian, using its normal computer hardware and software and technical expertise, and
(ii) creating the record would not unreasonably interfere with the operations of the custodian, and
(c) must provide, at the request of an applicant and if reasonably practicable, an explanation of any term, code or abbreviation used in the record.

6) Expressed wishes of individual

A patient has the ability to request the custodian to include additional instructions in their own EHR, such as the wish to keep certain information from disclosure.

56.4 In deciding how much prescribed health information to make accessible via the Alberta EHR, a regulated health professional or an authorized custodian must consider as an important factor any expressed wishes of the individual who is the subject of the prescribed health information relating to access to that information, together with any other factors the regulated health professional or authorized custodian considers important.

58(2) In deciding how much health information to disclose, a custodian must consider as an important factor any expressed wishes of the individual who is the subject of the information relating to disclosure of the information, together with any other factors the custodian considers relevant.

7) Right to refuse access to health information.

The custodian is bestowed with a discretionary powers in s 11 (1)(a) - (e) to refuse health information to an applicant if the disclosure:

- 1) could cause mental or physical health harm and threaten the safety of
 - the applicant.
 - another individual.
 - the public.
 - 2) compromises the identity of confidential sources of health information.
 - 3) reveals undisclosed information belonging to the Executive Council or the member's staff.
 - 4) reveals advice developed by or for health authorities or provincial health boards.
 - 5) prejudices the use or results of specific audits, diagnostic tests or assessments.¹³⁵
- Moreover, the custodian is also given a mandatory obligation in s 12 (2)(a) – (d) to refuse

health information to an applicant if disclosure involves:

1. information about a person other than the applicant.
2. procedures or results of an investigation of a health service professional.
3. data that reveals essential information of deliberations of executive council or treasury.
4. prohibition by another enactment of Alberta.

Case Law

Case laws are laws based on the outcomes of past cases. These are precedent-setting decisions that dictate how any acts or statutes will be interpreted by the courts. The common law in Alberta gives primacy to privacy over access.

There is a long standing rivalry between privacy rights or rights for accessing personal information. As in the case of *Covenant Health v Alberta*, 2014 ABQB 562 where a daughter of an elderly couple living at a health facility was restricted from her visitation privileges after interfering with her parent's care.¹³⁶ She then filed a Freedom of Information request to see all

¹³⁵ Health Information Act, RSA 2000, c H-5, <http://canlii.ca/t/52rj4>, retrieved on 2016-06-16.

¹³⁶ Dan Michaluk, "Alberta QB Deals with Scope of Application of Alberta Health Privacy Statute," *CanLII Connects*, last updated October 18, 2014, <http://canliiconnects.org/en/commentaries/30197>.

information the facility has collected and that may involve her. Justice Thomas Wakeling said “Openness is not the goal of the Health Information Act,” as he ruled in favour of protecting the privacy of the institution.¹³⁷

According to *McInerney v. MacDonald*, 1992 CanLII 57 (SCC), [1992] 2 SCR 138, the Supreme Court of Canada observed that there is a fiduciary relationship between the physician and patient.¹³⁸ While the HIA establishes that the patient is entitled to view their medical records, this fiduciary affiliation gives the physician—and in effect the custodian—the responsibility to withhold information stored. A patient accessing NetCare from home increases the chances of hacking through insecure online connections. Thus, the long process of paper application before granting access is justified to safeguard the patient’s health records from the risk of unauthorized access.

Moreover, in the case of *Martin v. Sievers*, 2014 ABQB 357, efficient access to justice does not necessitate expediency in access.¹³⁹ The doctor from the Independent Medical Examination was denied access to the Plaintiff’s medical records through NetCare even though it would have saved time and money—Court efficiency was possible during the production of the documents. The Court decided that quicker access to justice would undermine the judicial process with regards to fairness when it comes to the safeguards already in place for privacy.

¹³⁷ *Covenant Health v Alberta (Information and Privacy Commissioner)*, 2014 ABQB 562 (CanLII), <http://canlii.ca/t/g8zlg>, retrieved on 2016-06-16

¹³⁸ *McInerney v. MacDonald*, [1992] 2 SCR 138, 1992 CanLII 57 (SCC), <http://canlii.ca/t/1fsbl>, retrieved on 2016-06-16

¹³⁹ *Martin v Sievers*, 2014 ABQB 357 (CanLII), <http://canlii.ca/t/g7f4k>, retrieved on 2016-06-16

Policies and Guidelines

Health service providers are required by law to enact privacy and security policies and procedures.

Patients can access their EHRs, but only after many application hurdles,¹⁴⁰ lengthy delays and several fees.¹⁴¹ The applicant is expected to pay fees to cover the costs incurred by the provider in producing paper records, which is based on s 67 of the HIA: *Power to charge fees*. Moreover, the scope of the information is limited and any other file must be requested separately.

Physicians however, have immediate and complete access to all records. Thus, the argument is that patients should have similar privileges.

*NetCare Training Guideline*¹⁴²

A preparatory tool intended to train strategic staff members of facilities so they may pass on the teachings. A training for the trainers who are current or future custodians in NetCare.

Security Notice:

- *You are aware that AH monitors access to Alberta Netcare for security purposes and to protect the Information. By accessing Alberta Netcare you are expressly consenting to these monitoring activities.*

Security and Confidentiality

Only authorized users may access a person's medical and demographic data. EHR access is based on your user role and profession. Access permissions and other security credentials are set up to ensure you have enough information available for you to do your job, and that information is accessed only on a need to know basis. Be aware that Alberta Netcare Portal access is monitored and audited on a regular basis, as well as at the request of a patient, physician or manager. By accessing Alberta Netcare, you agree to be bound by the Terms of Use and Disclaimer (as noted on the Alberta Netcare Portal login page), and to comply with all application laws. The Terms of Use and Disclaimer states that Alberta Netcare Portal is for the use of authorized users only. Unauthorized access to Alberta Netcare Portal is prohibited and may result in disciplinary action.

¹⁴⁰ Patrick, Kirsten, "Patients and their medical records: it is time to embrace transparency," *Canadian Medical Association Journal* 186, no. 11 (2014): 811-811.

¹⁴¹ Darcy Henton, "Alberta To Open Limited Health Record Online Portal Before End Of Year," *Calgary Herald*, last updated January 15, 2015, <http://calgaryherald.com/news/politics/alberta-to-open-limited-health-record-online-portal-before-end-of-year>.

¹⁴² "Alberta Netcare: Super User Training Guide," *albertanetcare.ca*, version 1.3, October 2015, <http://www.albertanetcare.ca/learningcentre/documents/SuperUser-Training-Guide.pdf>.

There are restrictions of use such that the custodian makes three agreements:

- *You agree that the information in and accessible through Alberta Netcare (the "Information") is private and confidential and that you will take all reasonable steps to maintain the confidentiality of the Information. You further agree that you are aware of and will comply with the provisions of the Health Information Act and the Freedom of Information and Protection of Privacy Act, as applicable, with respect to the Information.*
- *You understand that a person, who knowingly collects, uses or discloses health or personal information in contravention of the Health Information Act or the Freedom of Information and Protection of Privacy Act may be found guilty of an offence and liable to a fine of up to \$100,000.*
- *You agree that you will not use the Information for commercial purposes.*

Also included in this article are Best Practices for custodians and affiliates:

1. *Never share your Alberta Netcare Portal User ID and/or password. You are responsible for all access and activity made under your User ID.*
2. *Only access health information necessary fulfill your job responsibilities, and keep this information confidential.*
3. *When you have finished using Alberta Netcare Portal, be sure to logout and exit out of the internet browser.*
4. *When printing information from a patient's EHR, follow the policy at your work site for the use and storage of these print-outs.*

[*Health Information Act Guidelines and Practices Manual*](#)

A publication that serves as a companion for the HIA with more explanations and detail.

[*Canadian Medical Association: Physician Guidelines for Online Communication with Patients*](#)

Outlines best practices for electronic communication. Information exchanged are encouraged to be for general purposes only.

1. Purpose of online communication include
 - Administrative uses
 - Education and health promotion
 - Patient care
 - *Receiving patient requests for prescription refills*
 - *Clarifying or reiterating instructions*
 - *Receiving and answering patient follow-up questions*
 - *Providing post-procedure instructions and follow-up*
 - *Notifying or reminding about routine tests and procedures*
 - *Monitoring*
 - *Providing test results (where acceptable)*
 - *Consulting related to conditions that have been previously discussed*
 - *Consulting related to new conditions*

2. *Response to patient inquiries—managing expectations*
 - *Establish reasonable response times — different enquiries may warrant different response times; account for responses during times of practice closure (weekends, vacations, statutory holidays)*
 - *Automatically acknowledge receipt of communications and indicate the protocol for response*
 - *Provide instructions about access to alternatives in case of emergency or urgent situations*
 - *Encourage or require the provision of a subject heading*
 - *Triage messages according to subject heading and establish a procedure for responding to each type*
 - *Limit time required to read and respond to patient communications by encouraging or requiring limited text from patients; restricting communications to single or simple issues; encouraging or requiring office visits for complex matters*
 - *Use templates to encourage or require standardized communication (with possible benefits regarding storage and linkage)*
 - *Publicize response times (on the physician’s web site, in an automated reply, in initial instructions to patients, in an agreement with patients); include instructions regarding emergencies or urgent instructions or in the event a response is not received within the specified time.*¹⁴³

To preserve privacy and confidentiality, the CMA also recommend that only secure systems should be used to transfer sensitive information. Adverse test results are better communicated in person to further explain the results and answer questions as they arise.

Alberta Health Services Policies and Guidelines

One of which is on Information and Privacy where they state that their purpose is:

- Ensuring AHS complies with legislation relating to the privacy and confidentiality of information that could identify an individual. This includes compliance with the Health Information Act (“HIA”) and the Freedom of Information and Protection of Privacy Act (“FOIP”).
- Handling AHS records management issues, other than those patient charts managed by Health Information Management.
- Training and education, as well as investigation of privacy breaches.
- Managing and responding to formal requests for access to information or for correction of information under the FOIP.
- Managing and responding to formal requests for correction of information under the HIA.
- Preparing and assisting programs in preparing privacy impact assessments.
- Working with researchers regarding access use or disclosure of confidential information
- *Providing advice and consultation services related to the HIA and FOIP.*¹⁴⁴

¹⁴³ Canadian Medical Association. "Physician guidelines for online communication with patients." *Ottawa: Canadian Medical Association* (2005).

¹⁴⁴ "Information and Privacy," *AlbertaHealthServices.ca*, accessed June 6, 2016, <http://www.albertahealthservices.ca/info/Page3934.aspx>

College of Physicians and Surgeons of Alberta (CPSA) Health Professionals Act Standard of Practice

In the standards of practice for Patient Record Content, when it comes to a patient's record, regulated members need to include:

- a. clinical notes for each patient encounter including:
 - i. presenting concern, relevant findings, assessment and plan, including follow-up when indicated;
 - ii. prescriptions issued, including drug name, dose, quantity prescribed, directions for use and refills issued;
 - iii. tests, referrals and consultations requisitioned, including those accepted and declined by the patient; and
 - iv. interactions with other databases such as the Alberta Electronic Health Record (Netcare).
- b. Information pertaining to the consent process;
- c. a cumulative patient profile (CPP) contextual to the physician-patient relationship (the longer and more complex the relationship the more extensive should be the record) detailing:
 - i. patient identification (i.e., name, address, phone number, personal health number, contact person in case of emergencies);
 - ii. current medications and treatments, including complementary and alternative therapies;
 - iii. allergies and drug reactions;
 - iv. ongoing health conditions and identified risk factors;
 - v. medical history, including family medical history;
 - vi. social history (e.g., occupation, life events, habits);
 - vii. health maintenance plans (immunizations, disease surveillance, screening tests); and
 - viii. date the CPP was last updated;
- d. laboratory, imaging, pathology and consultation reports;
- e. operative records, procedural records and discharge summaries;
- f. any communication with the patient concerning the patient's medical care, including unplanned face-to-face contacts;
- g. a six-year history of patient billing encounter data as required by Alberta Health (identifying type of service, date of service and fee(s) charged); and
- h. a record of missed and/or cancelled appointments.¹⁴⁵

¹⁴⁵ College of Physicians and Surgeons of Alberta (CPSA) Council, "Standards of Practice: Patient Record Content," *cpsa.ca*, last updated January 2016, <http://www.cpsa.ca/standardspractice/patient-record-content/>.

Analysis

The Letter of the Law

The privacy and access laws laid out in the Privacy Act and the Freedom of Information and Protection of Privacy Act overlap with the HIA. No relevant information beyond the HIA is offered. Thus, the HIA is the predominant legislation for reference in Alberta when it comes to health information. The HIA is clear in its purpose for granting health care providers access to a patient's health information along with strong support for information sharing between authorized providers. The legislation repeatedly emphasizes the custodian's obligation to maintain appropriate use, collection and disclosure of health information. There is also support for integration between custodians and affiliates who have access to NetCare. Gaining entry to NetCare can only be done by completing a Privacy Impact Assessment, which is important to ensure consistent standards are maintained with regards to protecting the privacy of patients and the security of the EHR system. There is also opportunity for using the information in this EHR system for secondary use such as research.

While most of the HIA is established to protect individuals and their health information, patients have the right to access their records. The Custodian is obligated to comply with a request for disclosure, yet there are circumstances when denial is discretionary or even mandatory.

The Spirit of the Law

The spirit of the law is the original intention behind a legislation, which is often preferred in the court proceedings over the letter of the law—interpretation of meaning only from what is

written.¹⁴⁶ It is interesting to note the language chosen for the HIA. When it comes to health information in the HIA, it is difficult to distinguish between use and disclosure, but for the purposes of this legislation, sharing between custodians and affiliates is deemed as 'use,' while sharing beyond that is considered information 'disclosure.' This sets the tone that the complete ownership of the health records falls in the hands of the custodian.

The spirit of the law is clearly determined when examining case laws. A provincial Court making a judgment against a request for access sets the precedent for privacy rights.¹⁴⁷ This is especially true when the individual's information involved the health records of someone else, thus access to all the information is denied.¹⁴⁸ Using s 4(1)(u) of the FOIPPA, information that falls under the HIA is deemed health information, and because access rights and privacy rights are mutually exclusive, therefore, privacy takes precedents over access. When it comes to PHRs and allowing access to health records through NetCare, then a case only needs to be made that the health of others is involved, which would justify non-disclosure pursuant s 11 of the HIA.

The policies and guidelines set by NetCare and the CMA are consistent with this understanding of the HIA in that patients—the custodian is the gatekeeper to restrict entry. Moreover, the HIA does create room for the sharing of information by using general language—an important feature of legislation so it may not be restrictive in future circumstances. However, the interpretation of the legislation has taken a different tone as policies are consistently written according to the Case Laws that set the precedent for privacy over access.

¹⁴⁶ Doreen McBarnet, and Christopher Whelan, "The elusive spirit of the law: Formalism and the struggle for legal control," *The Modern Law Review* 54, no. 6 (1991): 848-873.

¹⁴⁷ *Covenant Health v Alberta (Information and Privacy Commissioner)*, 2014 ABQB 562 (CanLII). <http://canlii.ca/t/g8zlg>, retrieved on 2016-06-16

¹⁴⁸ *Ibid.*

There is great inefficiencies that need to be corrected in Alberta's health information system, whether it is the disintegrated sharing of information that leaves a patient with multiple records, or the long-paper-based process for a patients to gain access. Any existing barriers need to be removed in order to establish fairness. No amendments to the law are necessary since the law is not restrictive, yet policies need to be adjusted accordingly.

With regards to information sharing between providers and working toward a single patient record in NetCare, the law supports such initiatives as long as each provider has completed an application for the Privacy Impact Assessment as mentioned earlier. The only hindrance in this case would be that providers who have to adjust their work routines accordingly, which will require the support of policies and guidelines to be laid out in the *NetCare Training Guide*, the *Canadian Medical Association (CMA) Code of Ethics*, *Alberta Health Services Policies and Guidelines* and the *College of Physicians and Surgeons (CPSA) Health Professions Act Standards of Practice*.

With regards to the PHR, the law does not interfere with having a patient portal so long as the health information of the patient is kept safe. Providers would have to continue using the same precautions to protect this information. Technical solutions can help with the deployment of exceptions to access such as when information access must be denied during situations mentioned earlier—as laid out in the law. Policies need to lay out the code of practice for health care providers to guide how PHRs will be used. Providers need to be reassured that patients viewing a single patient record of their own complies with current legislation. These policies will set the foundation for moving Alberta's current health path toward patient-centred care.

CHAPTER 6: PROPOSED SOLUTION BASED ON KAISER'S

The Current Health Information System is Linear

Figure 10. Current linear health information system in Alberta. Note, EMRs are electronic medical records, which are digital information of the typical paper-based medical record for patients

The current health information is linear (Figure 10). Health data is collected unilaterally, starting from the patient at the point-of-care—hospitals, laboratories, testing facilities, pharmacies and clinics. Any health information on record is only recorded by health care providers. The information is securely sent to an EHR system, which is directly linked to the NetCare system. The health care providers interacting with a patient may access the EHR that is available in NetCare, thus the two way sharing of EHR information between health providers and NetCare. Similarly, hospital discharge summaries are inputted into the NetCare system, while hospitals and surgeons have easy access to the provincial EHR. There is an interoperable system with EHRs, where information flows between the NetCare portal and multiple-health care providers.

However, there is no sharing of EMRs—electronic medical records, which are digital copies of the information from typical paper-based medical record. Each doctor or specialist holds a non-integrated medical records and paper charts of their patients at their clinic. That is, EMRs rarely get entered into the NetCare system and usually stay at the clinic. Similarly, hospital information such as progress reports, medical records and administrative reports do not make it into the EHR system. Hospital charts are paper-based medical records that are similar to clinical EMRs in that they are outside of the NetCare and EHR systems.

In summary, health information system currently has the provider at its centre. It is a linear system in that it flows unidirectionally from the patient and into the health system. EHRs from health care providers are interconnected with the NetCare system while EMRs are not.

The Health Information System Cycle

Figure 11. The ideal goal of unified EHR system with an efficient health information life cycle

It is ideal to have a life cycle of health information that allows room for both PHRs and a feedback mechanism for operational efficiency (Figure 11). For simplification, let us say the patient entering the point of care would be the starting point where information is first entered into the system. It is in the form of an EHR or EMR. These records are then entered into the NetCare system, where the health care professional has access to past records from other providers (the health care team with their own EHRs or EMRs). Thus, NetCare serves as a complete EHR and a shared-provincial record.

The PHR gateway should allow the patient to obtain their EHRs in the NetCare network. Patients will have full ownership of this PHR and will be able to input their health information and monitoring results. Yet not all information will be shared or at least immediately. Physicians currently have the ability to mask certain records from being disclosed to the patient; for example, sensitive records in a mental health history that may lead to harm. This masking option should be retained before full disclosure into the PHR. It would also be ideal to incorporate an option to delay displaying certain information, such as diagnostic results for a cancer patient, to avoid any concerns regarding misunderstandings that may arise before face-to-face appointments. A notification function should remind the physician's office of the need to set up an appointment to disclose that information to the patient.

Another masking option could also be available to the patient in the PHR—the current system allows for this option. At the moment, a person may have some information masked so that not everything is visible when a record is accessed.¹⁴⁹ In the new model, patients may mask

¹⁴⁹ "Common Questions From Albertans - Alberta Netcare," *Albertanetcare.ca*, accessed September 1, 2016, <http://www.albertanetcare.ca/CommonQuestions.htm>.

certain sensitive information, such a pregnancy miscarriage, in order to protect the privacy of the patient from proxies gaining access to the PHR. A patient may also have a direct connection to their health care provider, whether through secure messaging, reminders or scheduling appointments.

Continued efficiency improvement is only possible by allowing a gateway for secondary use—system maintenance, research, audits, budgeting, health system planning and performance analysis. Alberta NetCare does not allow for access for secondary use beyond research purposes.¹⁵⁰ In the new ideal model, secondary use is possible through the de-identification of patient information. The current health care culture preserves EHRs from NetCare to be used for primary care purposes only. Adding an option for secondary use would require physician buy-in who may not see the immediate benefits of secondary use. The benefits of having this additional gateway for health information sharing must be communicated so that providers appreciate the value in participating. Continuous improvement should always be a long term goal of any health information cycle.¹⁵¹

In summary, the ideal health information system should promote patient-centred care by including individuals in the data sharing loop. NetCare should be established as a provincial-wide EHR with a complete patient record readily available to all stakeholders. Health care providers must input EMRs and EHRs into a consolidated and accessible system. This new

¹⁵⁰ "Using EHR Data For Research - Alberta Netcare," *Albertanetcare.ca*, accessed September 1, 2016, <http://www.albertanetcare.ca/Research.htm>.

¹⁵¹ Gary Kaplan, Lopez MH, McGinnis JM, et al., "Transforming Health Care Scheduling and Access: Getting to Now," *Military Medicine*, 181(7), pp. 613–614. [Committee on Optimizing Scheduling in Health Care; *Institute of Medicine*; Transforming Health Care Scheduling and Access: Getting to Now. Washington (DC): National Academies Press (US); 2015 Aug 24. 3.

structure requires a PHR for patients as well as an avenue for secondary use of the NetCare records for achieving continuous improvements in operational efficiency.

A Successful Story

It is difficult to write about successful milestones in health care without mentioning Kaiser Permanente in California. The Affordable Care Act as well as the meaningful use incentive program established by the HITEC Act in 2009 promoted health information integration between providers. Adoption rates have soared in recent years due to the backing of governments, health providers and patients, to the point that PHR use is projected to be at 75 percent in four years (Figure 12).¹⁵²

Figure 12. Projected adoption rates for PHRs in the United States as a result of introducing the meaningful use incentive program¹⁵³

The barriers and problems the American health care system faces in comparison to Canada's could be equated to the population differences—they are tenfold. The message is

¹⁵² Eric W. Ford, Bradford W. Hesse, and Timothy R. Huerta, "Personal Health Record Use in the United States: Forecasting Future Adoption Levels," *Journal of medical Internet research* 18, no. 3 (2016).

¹⁵³ *Ibid.*

simple: in order to adopt new and proven tools in health care, you need everyone on board.

The meaningful use initiative emphasized involving consumers from the development stages of the PHR system and up to this point today. The common theme during promotion was bringing value to providers, patients and caregivers.

Another theme was achieving a big goal in stages (Figure 13).¹⁵⁴ The initial roll-out of the program in 2011 involved data capture and sharing while working toward a single-patient record—they are still far from that goal despite great progress. The first stage involved e-prescribing, and the sharing of lab results and clinical summaries. The second stage was to advance clinical processes by incorporating rigorous information exchange, more robust electronic communication and patient-controlled information through a PHR. Stage three revolves around improving clinical outcomes by introducing seamless surveillance and having a comprehensive patient record.

¹⁵⁴ "Meaningful Use," *Dhss.Alaska.Gov*. State of Alaska, accessed September 1, 2016, <http://dhss.alaska.gov/HIT/Meaningfuluse/Pages/Default.aspx>.

Figure 13. Meaningful use incentive program divided into stages¹⁵⁵

Kaiser Permanente is special however since they were able to adopt a PHR—My Health Manager—in 2007 to all of its members. They saw the benefits of PHR use outweighing the privacy concerns, especially since the project was user-friendly and useful for care.¹⁵⁶ The study by Ford et al (2016) used Kaiser Permanente’s data to develop an S-curve that forecasts significant PHR adoption by 2020 (Figure 12).¹⁵⁷ They concluded that the ambitious adoption and functionality capabilities should be used again as future milestones are being developed.

¹⁵⁵ Eric W. Ford, Bradford W. Hesse, and Timothy R. Huerta, "Personal Health Record Use in the United States: Forecasting Future Adoption Levels," *Journal of medical Internet research* 18, no. 3 (2016).

¹⁵⁶ Robert Redling, "Personal Health Record Usage And Medical Practices," *Physicianspractice.Com*, , last updated October 5, 2012, <http://www.physicianspractice.com/personal-health-records/personal-health-record-usage-and-medical-practices>.

¹⁵⁷ Eric W. Ford, Bradford W. Hesse, and Timothy R. Huerta, "Personal Health Record Use in the United States: Forecasting Future Adoption Levels," *Journal of medical Internet research* 18, no. 3 (2016).

CHAPTER 7: POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

In order to affect change that is evidence based, it would be effective to follow the Meaningful Use Incentive Program. This should be similarly done with a staged approach. Alberta's health information system needs to shift from a linear model (Figure 10) to a more cyclical model of co-ownership, where there is a unified patient-health record (Figure 11). To that end, it is recommended that the Ministry of Health follows the following nine steps in annual increments of three. Each step must be initiated within one year to ensure the momentum carries.

Year One: 2016-2017

- 1) Develop a code of practice for health care providers for integrating medical records and EHRs into the provincially-consolidated system—NetCare. This step must include collaboration between representatives of government, health care providers, researchers, and patient groups. Emphasis should be placed on privacy and how the law will remain unchanged and the privacy stipulations of current practice carry on. Providers should be reassured that encryption techniques and following the current code of conduct around privacy will secure health information.
- 2) Develop a portal adoption policy that outlines the expectations for PHR use by the patient. Patients are expected to fill their personal and demographic information. Everyone should have a portal set up yet it is up to the physicians to encourage its use. The value of the PHR should be demonstrated to both patients and providers. Patients

should be reassured that the current privacy legislation is still relevant and confers protection.

- 3) Introduce access to the pharmacy information network for prescription refills, viewing past and present medications, treatment regimens, drug information and relevant information manuals. Patients should also be given the ability to arrange appointments.

Year Two: 2017-2018

- 4) Introduce an ability to view lab results and input data into the system so it may be accessed by health providers
- 5) Create a system that makes secondary use of health information for quality improvement and training purposes.
- 6) Create a PHR training program for both patients and health professionals with a strong argument that demonstrates value to all parties involved.

Year Three: 2018-2019

- 7) Implement a support system for change management as health care providers adjust to the change. It would be preferred that operational use is seamless and automated
- 8) Develop a secure messaging system for patient-provider communication.
- 9) Allow patients full access to their EHR through NetCare

Measuring Success

As with any effective development, policies should follow a cyclical process of refinement. The following is adapted from Miljan (2012) on what constitutes an ideal policy process (Figure 14).¹⁵⁸ A policy is initially devised based on an identified need and a clear understanding of what the problem is. The next step is to make a case for an option and develop a plan based on the analysis. This stage is where the current recommendations laid out in this paper fall. Next is the need to implement the recommendations based on specified details and plans—as mentioned in the previous recommendation section. However, a critical part of this process is to re-evaluate the policy after the implementation, which necessitates having specific measures for success during the initial development of the policy.

Figure 14. The ideal policy process is cyclical with refinements along the way and an evaluation after implementation.

¹⁵⁸ Lydia Miljan, *Public policy in Canada: An introduction*. Oxford University Press, 2012.

Specific gauges of success include the measures used in the Meaningful Use initiative such as: the numbers of added EMRs to NetCare, usability measures for patient portals, provider surveys on organizational change, provider surveys on patient outcomes, measuring information system usefulness and qualitative constructivist interviews and analysis.¹⁵⁹ These measures of success are important to monitor after policy deployment so that adjustments can be made accordingly.

Further considerations

The concept of public policy is situated between economics and politics,¹⁶⁰ where scarce goods and resources are allocated according to a preconceived understanding of necessity—based on certain platforms and interests. Thus, a critical component of policy recommendations would be to understand the economic value of change and frame this benefit in a way that is consistent with political goals or agendas.

A cost-benefit analysis should be done for the long term effects of information sharing and PHR adoption. This analysis will be useful in making the case for other jurisdictions in Canada and possibly national implementation. The ultimate goal would be to create a national health information ecosystem that promotes interoperability, which creates a single patient record for individuals to take along with them as they travel. This initiative would require aligning policies and professional codes of conduct to allow for interoperability between provinces and territories.

¹⁵⁹ Kimberly W Bartholomew, "Patient Portals: Achieving Technology Acceptance and Meaningful Use in Independent Physician-Managed Practices," *Nova Southeastern University*, (2016).

¹⁶⁰ *Ibid.*

CHAPTER 8: CONCLUSION

As we move closer to a new year of groundbreaking initiatives in health care, Alberta should be in the forefront of patient-centred health based on holistic, collaborative and responsive care. A single patient record that is accessible through a PHR system is the first step.

After examining the health information system in Alberta, we can safely say that the barriers to implementing change in the province are manageable. Although there are some concerns with having a PHR system in Alberta, the benefits seem to outweigh the costs. The barriers to adoption have been identified and are manageable. Alberta is closer than any other province to achieving a single patient record and eventually a province-wide PHR, however, we found that there is limited literature on the cost-benefit analysis to garner national support. To obtain widespread support and eventually adoption nationally, the strengths and weaknesses of other solutions must be systematically evaluated against alternative solutions.

We also surveyed the current policies and laws currently laid out in Alberta around health information sharing and determined that the legislation is flexible enough to allow for a single patient record and a PHR. Policies should be amended to allow for such change and make it a priority. Solutions from abroad offer insight to how these policies can be structured. We recommended following the American framework—the Meaningful Use initiative—since it has shown significant progress. The policy framework proposed is realistic and compliant with current legislation. The only question that remains is how to ensure the inherent value of such changes is internalized by both patients and providers.

The current health information is a linear model where patients enter the health system and data is collected from them and shared on behalf of the individual. The system, and in effect the patient's record, is disintegrated as clinicians have their own data that is not being incorporated into the provincial-electronic health record—NetCare. The proposed cyclical model creates a paradigm shift where all health care providers and patients are on the same page.

Bibliography

- "Alberta Netcare Portal Links Circle Of Care For Alberta Patients - Canada Health Infoway," *Infoway-Inforoute.Ca*, accessed May 13, 2016, <https://www.infoway-inforoute.ca/en/209-what-we-do/digital-health-and-you/stories/94-alberta-netcare-portal-links-circle-of-care-for-alberta-patients>.
- "Alberta Netcare: Super User Training Guide." *albertanetcare.ca*. Version 1.3. October 2015. <http://www.albertanetcare.ca/learningcentre/documents/SuperUser-Training-Guide.pdf>.
- "Benefits to Health Professionals - Alberta Netcare." *Albertanetcare.Ca*. Accessed May 13, 2016. <http://www.albertanetcare.ca/Benefits.htm>.
- "Common Questions From Albertans - Alberta Netcare." *Albertanetcare.Ca*. Accessed September 1, 2016. <http://www.albertanetcare.ca/CommonQuestions.htm>.
- "Engaging the Patient in Healthcare: An Overview of Personal Health Record Systems and Implications for Alberta." *albertahealthservices.ca*, last modified 2009.
- "Experiences of Clinicians Adopting Health ICTs in Canada - Canada Health Infoway." *Infoway-Inforoute.Ca*. Accessed May 13, 2016. <https://www.infoway-inforoute.ca/en/communities/pan-canadian-clinician-peer-network/experiences-of-clinicians-adopting-health-icts-in-canada>.
- "Information and Privacy." *AlbertaHealthServices.ca*. Accessed June 6, 2016. <http://www.albertahealthservices.ca/info/Page3934.aspx>.
- "Jurisdictional Peer-To-Peer Networks - Canada Health Infoway." *Infoway-Inforoute.Ca*. Accessed May 13, 2016. <https://www.infoway-inforoute.ca/en/communities/pan-canadian-clinician-peer-network/jurisdictional-peer-to-peer-networks>.
- "Managing My Personal Health Record: My Story of Living with Lupus." *Health IT Buzz*. Last modified May 13, 2013. <https://www.healthit.gov/buzz-blog/electronic-health-and-medical-records/managing-personal-health-record-story-living-lupus/>.
- "Meaningful Use." *Dhss.Alaska.Gov*. State of Alaska. Accessed September 1, 2016. <http://dhss.alaska.gov/HIT/Meaningfuluse/Pages/Default.aspx>.
- "Netcare Learning Centre: Alberta Netcare Portal (ANP)." *Alberta Government*. Accessed January 03, 2009. <http://www.albertanetcare.ca/learningcentre/Alberta-Netcare-Portal.htm>.

"Patient Portals and E-Views - Canada Health Infoway." *Canada Health Infoway*. Accessed May 1, 2016. Infoway-Inforoute.ca. <https://www.infoway-inforoute.ca/en/solutions/consumer-e-services/patient-portals-and-e-views>.

"Privacy and Security." *albertanetcare.ca*. Accessed June 6, 2016. <http://www.albertanetcare.ca/PatientPrivacy.htm>.

"Sunnybrook Health Sciences Centre expanding MyChart online services to Family Practice Patients." *Nexj.com*. February 26, 2013. <http://www.nexj.com/2013/02/26/sunnybrook-health-sciences-centre-expanding-mychart-online-services-to-family-practice-patients/>.

"Symposium to explore ways to unleash health-care innovation in Canada." University of Calgary. Last modified October 26, 2015, <https://www.ucalgary.ca/utoday/issue/2015-10-26/symposium-explore-ways-unleash-health-care-innovation-canada>.

"Using EHR Data for Research - Alberta Netcare," *Albertanetcare.ca*. Accessed September 1, 2016. <http://www.albertanetcare.ca/Research.htm>.

"Welcome to Alberta Netcare." *Alberta Government*. Accessed January 03, 2009, <http://www.albertanetcare.ca/>.

Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality Partnership for Patients. "Interim Update on 2013 Annual Hospital-Acquired Condition Rate and Estimates of Cost Savings and Deaths Averted From 2010 to 2013." Accessed May 13, 2016. <http://www.ahrq.gov/professionals/quality-patient-safety/pfp/interimhacrate2013.html>.

Alberta Health Services. "An Overview of Alberta's Electronic Health Record Information System." 2013. Accessed December 22, 2015. http://www.albertanetcare.ca/documents/An_Overview_of_Albertas_ERHIS.pdf. P. 12.

Alberta Health Services. "Engaging the Patient in Healthcare: An Overview of Personal Health Record Systems and Implications for Alberta." *White Paper*. 2009.

American Hospital Association. "Individual's Ability to Electronically Access their Hospital Medical Records, Perform Key Tasks is Growing." *Trendwatch*. July 2016. <http://www.aha.org/research/reports/tw/chartbook/2012/chart2-9.pdf>.

Ammenwerth, Elske, Petra Schnell-Inderst, and Alexander Hoerbst. "The impact of electronic patient portals on patient care: a systematic review of controlled trials." *Journal of medical Internet research*. 14, no. 6 (2012): e162.

- Anderson, Robert M., Martha M. Funnell, Patricia M. Butler, Marilyn S. Arnold, James T. Fitzgerald, and Catherine C. Feste. "Patient empowerment: results of a randomized controlled trial." *Diabetes care* 18, no. 7 (1995): 943-949.
- Archer, N., U. Fevrier-Thomas, Cynthia Lokker, K. Ann McKibbin, and S. E. Straus. "Personal health records: a scoping review." *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association*. 18, no. 4 (2011): 515-522.
- Bartholomew, Kimberly W. "Patient Portals: Achieving Technology Acceptance and Meaningful Use in Independent Physician-Managed Practices." (2016).
- Baxter, Siyan, Kristy Sanderson, Alison J. Venn, C. Leigh Blizzard, and Andrew J. Palmer. "The relationship between return on investment and quality of study methodology in workplace health promotion programs." *American Journal of Health Promotion*. 28, no. 6 (2014): 347-363.
- Blomqvist, Ake and Colin Busby. "The Naylor Report and Health Policy: Canada Needs a New Model." *CD Howe Institute E-Brief*. 240 (2016).
- Broman, Kristy Kummerow, Omobolanle O. Oyefule, Sharon E. Phillips, Rebeccah B. Baucom, Michael D. Holzman, Kenneth W. Sharp, Richard A. Pierce, William H. Nealon, and Benjamin K. Poulouse. "Postoperative care using a secure online patient portal: changing the (inter) face of general surgery." *Journal of the American College of Surgeons* 221, no. 6 (2015): 1057-1066.
- Burns, T., J. Catty, S. White, S. Clement, G. Ellis, I. Rees Jones, P. Lissouba, S. McLaren, D. Rose, and T. Wykes. "Continuity of care in mental health: understanding and measuring a complex phenomenon." *Psychological medicine* 39, no. 02 (2009): 313-323.
- Cahill Jennifer E., Mark R. Gilbert, and Terri S. Armstrong. "Personal health records as portal to the electronic medical record." *Journal of Neuro-oncology*. 117, no. 1 (2014): 1-6.
- Canada Health Infoway. "Patient Portals and E-Views - Canada Health Infoway." *Infoway-Inforoute.ca*. Accessed May 13, 2016. <https://www.infoway-inforoute.ca/en/solutions/consumer-e-services/patient-portals-and-e-views>.
- College of Physicians and Surgeons of Alberta (CPSA) Council. "Standards of Practice: Patient Record Content." *cpsa.ca*. Last updated January 2016. <http://www.cpsa.ca/standardspractice/patient-record-content/>.
- Canadian Medical Association. "Physician guidelines for online communication with patients." *Ottawa: Canadian Medical Association* (2005).

Chumblor, Neale R., David Haggstrom, and Jason J. Saleem. "Implementation of health information technology in Veterans Health Administration to support transformational

Comstock, Jonah. "OpenNotes will use \$10 million infusion for improved website, patient advocate outreach." *MobiHealthNews*. Last modified December 16, 2015. <http://mobihealthnews.com/content/opennotes-will-use-10-million-infusion-improved-website-patient-advocate-outreach>.

Conference Board of Canada. "Valuing Time Saved: Assessing the Impact of Patient Time Saved from the Adoption of Consumer Health Solutions." *infoway-inforoute.ca*. Last modified September 19, 2012. <https://www.infoway-inforoute.ca/en/component/edocman/resources/other/504-valuing-time-saved>.

Covenant Health v Alberta (Information and Privacy Commissioner). 2014 ABQB 562 (CanLII). <http://canlii.ca/t/g8zlg>, retrieved on 2016-06-16.

de la Torre-Díez, Isabel, Miguel López-Coronado, Cesar Vaca, Jesús Saez Aguado, and Carlos de Castro. "Cost-utility and cost-effectiveness studies of telemedicine, electronic, and mobile health systems in the literature: a systematic review." *Telemedicine and e-Health* 21, no. 2 (2015): 81-85.

de Lusignan, Simon, Freda Mold, Aziz Sheikh, Azeem Majeed, Jeremy C. Wyatt, Tom Quinn, Mary Cavill et al. "Patients' online access to their electronic health records and linked online services: a systematic interpretative review." *BMJ open*. 4, no. 9 (2014): e006021.

Delbanco, Tom, Jan Walker, Sigall K. Bell, Jonathan D. Darer, Joann G. Elmore, Nadine Farag, Henry J. Feldman et al. "Inviting patients to read their doctors' notes: a quasi-experimental study and a look ahead." *Annals of internal medicine* 157, no. 7 (2012): 461-470.

Detmer, Don, Meryl Bloomrosen, Brian Raymond, and Paul Tang. "Integrated personal health records: transformative tools for consumer-centric care." *BMC medical informatics and decision making*. 8, no. 1 (2008): 1.

Devkota, Bishnu, Joanne Salas, Sarah Sayavong, and Jeffrey F. Scherrer. "Use of an online patient portal and glucose control in primary care patients with diabetes." *Population health management*. 19, no. 2 (2016): 125-131.

Dinev, Tamara, Valentina Albano, Heng Xu, Alessandro D'Atri, and Paul Hart. "Individuals' Attitudes Towards Electronic Health Records: A Privacy Calculus Perspective." In *Advances in Healthcare Informatics and Analytics*. 19-50. Springer International Publishing. 2016.

- Diotte, Kerry. "Province's Health Records at Issue." *Daily Herald Tribune*. Last modified July 9, 2009. <http://www.dailyheraldtribune.com/2009/07/09/provinces-health-records-at-issue>.
- Emery, Herbert J.C., Kenneth Fyie, Ludovic Brunel, and Daniel Dutton. "The Fiscal, social and economic dividends of feeling better and living longer." *SPP Research Paper 6-20* (2013).
- Ford, Eric W., Bradford W. Hesse, and Timothy R. Huerta. "Personal Health Record Use in the United States: Forecasting Future Adoption Levels." *Journal of medical Internet research*. 18, no. 3 (2016).
- Kahn, James S., Veenu Aulakh, and Adam Bosworth. "What it takes: characteristics of the ideal personal health record." *Health affairs*. 28, no. 2 (2009): 369-376.
- Kaplan, Gary, Lopez MH, McGinnis JM, et al. "Transforming Health Care Scheduling and Access: Getting to Now." *Military Medicine*. 181(7), pp. 613–614. [Committee on Optimizing Scheduling in Health Care; *Institute of Medicine*; Transforming Health Care Scheduling and Access: Getting to Now. Washington (DC): National Academies Press (US); 2015 Aug 24. 3.]
- Kruse, Clemens Scott, Katy Bolton, and Greg Freriks. "The effect of patient portals on quality outcomes and its implications to meaningful use: a systematic review." *Journal of medical Internet research* 17, no. 2 (2015): e44.
- Gardner, E. "Will patient portals open the door to better care?" *Health data management* 18, no. 3 (2010): 58.
- Gastin, Lawrence O. "Health Information Privacy." *Cornell Law Review*. 1995, 80(3). <http://scholarship.law.cornell.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=2549&context=clr>
- Gerein Keith. "Massive Health Information Overhaul Coming To Alberta." *Edmonton Journal*. Last updated April 18, 2016. <http://edmontonjournal.com/news/local-news/massive-health-information-overhaul-coming-to-alberta>.
- Gheorghiu, Bobby and Simon Hagens. "Measuring interoperable EHR adoption and maturity: a Canadian example." *BMC medical informatics and decision making*. 16, no. 1 (2016): 1.
- Gibbons M. Christopher, Renee F. Wilson, Lipika Samal, Christoph U. Lehmann, Kay Dickersin, Harold P. Lehmann, Hanan Aboumatar et al. "Impact of consumer health informatics Applications." *Evidence Reports/Technology Assessments*. No. 188 (2009).
- Giroso, Federico, Robin C. Meili, and Richard Scoville. "Estimating the Benefit of HIT: Extrapolating evidence of health information technology savings and costs. Rand Corporation, 2005, 23.

- Goldzweig, Caroline Lubick, Greg Orshansky, Neil M. Paige, Ali Alexander Towfigh, David A. Haggstrom, Isomi Miake-Lye, Jessica M. Beroes, and Paul G. Shekelle. "Electronic patient portals: evidence on health outcomes, satisfaction, efficiency, and attitudes: a systematic review." *Annals of internal medicine* 159, no. 10 (2013): 677-687.
- Gordon, Nancy P. and Mark C. Hornbrook. "Differences in access to and preferences for using patient portals and other eHealth technologies based on race, ethnicity, and age: a database and survey study of seniors in a large health plan." *Journal of medical Internet research* 18, no. 3 (2016).
- Greenhalgh, Trisha, Susan Hinder, Katja Stramer, Tanja Bratan, and Jill Russell. "Adoption, non-adoption, and abandonment of a personal electronic health record: case study of HealthSpace." *Bmj* 341 (2010): c5814.
- Griffin A., A. Skinner, J. Thornhill, and M. Weinberger. "Patient Portals." *Applied Clinical Informatics* 7, no. 2 (2016): 489-501.
- Grünloh, Christiane, Åsa Cajander, and Gunilla Myreteg. "'The Record is our Work Tool!'- Physicians' Framing of a Patient Portal in Sweden." *Journal of Medical Internet Research*. (2016).
- Halamka, John D., Kenneth D. Mandl, and Paul C. Tang. "Early experiences with personal health Records." *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association* 15, no. 1 (2008): 1-7.
- Henton, Darcy. "Alberta To Open Limited Health Record Online Portal Before End Of Year." *Calgary Herald*. Last updated January 15, 2015.
<http://calgaryherald.com/news/politics/alberta-to-open-limited-health-record-online-portal-before-end-of-year>.
- HIMSS Board of Directors. "Interoperability Definition and Background." *Healthcare Information and Management Systems Society*. (2005).
<http://www.himss.org/sites/himssorg/files/HIMSSorg/Content/files/AUXILIOHIMSSInteroperabilityDefined.pdf>.
- Honeyman, Alasdair, Benita Cox, and Brian Fisher. "Potential impacts of patient access to their electronic care records." *Journal of Innovation in Health Informatics*. 13, no. 1 (2005): 55-60.
- Jodie, Sinnema. "Electronic Health Record System Will Cost Hundreds of Millions, But Is Vital, Government Official Says." *Edmonton Journal*. Last updated Feb 4, 2016.
<http://edmontonjournal.com/news/politics/electronic-health-record-system-will-cost-hundreds-of-million-but-is-vital-government-official-says>.

- Kaelber, David and Eric C. Pan. "The value of personal health record (PHR) systems," In *AMIA Annual Symposium Proceedings*, vol. 2008, p. 343, American Medical Informatics Association, 2008.
- Kharrazi, Hadi, Robin Chisholm, Dean VanNasdale, and Benjamin Thompson. "Mobile personal health records: An evaluation of features and functionality." *International journal of medical informatics*. 81, no. 9 (2012): 579-593.
- Kirsten, Patrick. "Patients and their medical records: it is time to embrace Transparency." *Canadian Medical Association Journal*. 186, no. 11 (2014): 811-811.
- Kruse, Clemens Scott, Katy Bolton, and Greg Freriks. "The effect of patient portals on quality outcomes and its implications to meaningful use: a systematic review." *Journal of medical Internet research* 17, no. 2 (2015): e44.
- Landon, Bruce E. "Keeping score under a global payment system." *New England Journal of Medicine*. 366, no. 5 (2012): 393-395.
- Levinson, Wendy, Audiey Kao, Alma Kuby, and Ronald A. Thisted. "Not all patients want to participate in decision making." *Journal of general internal medicine*. 20, no. 6 (2005): 531-535.
- Loria, Gaby. "What Makes A Great Patient Portal? Top Benefits, Features and Implementation Tips." *Software Advice*. Accessed May 13, 2016.
<http://www.softwareadvice.com/resources/patient-portals-top-benefits-features/>.
- Lorig, Kate R. and Halsted R. Holman. "Self-management education: history, definition, outcomes, and mechanisms." *Annals of behavioral medicine* 26. No. 1 (2003): 1-7.
- Lorig, Kate R., Peter D. Mazonson, and Halsted R. Holman. "Evidence suggesting that health education for self-management in patients with chronic arthritis has sustained health benefits while reducing health care costs." *Arthritis & Rheumatism* 36. No. 4 (1993): 439-446.
- Martin v Sievers. 2014 ABQB 357 (CanLII). <http://canlii.ca/t/g7f4k>. Retrieved on 2016-06-16.
- McBarnet, Doreen and Christopher Whelan. "The elusive spirit of the law: Formalism and the struggle for legal control." *The Modern Law Review*. 54, no. 6 (1991): 848-873.
- McInerney v. MacDonald. [1992] 2 SCR 138. 1992 CanLII 57 (SCC). <http://canlii.ca/t/1fsbl>. Retrieved on 2016-06-16.

Michaluk, Dan. "Alberta QB Deals with Scope of Application of Alberta Health Privacy Statute." *CanLII Connects*. Last updated October 18, 2014. <http://canliiconnects.org/en/commentaries/30197>.

Miljan, Lydia. *Public policy in Canada: An introduction*. Oxford University Press, 2012.

Miller Jr, David P., Celine Latulipe, Kathryn A. Melius, Sara A. Quandt, and Thomas A. Arcury. "Primary Care Providers' Views of Patient Portals: Interview Study of Perceived Benefits and Consequences." *Journal of medical Internet research* 18, no. 1 (2016).

Naylor, David, F. Girard, J. Mintz, N. Fraser, T. Jenkins, and C. Power. "Unleashing Innovation: Excellent Healthcare for Canada." *Report of the Advisory Panel on Healthcare Innovation*. (2015). <http://www.hc-sc.gc.ca/hcs-sss/innovation/index-eng.php> Okubo, Tracy.

Nazi, Kim M., Carolyn L. Turvey, Dawn M. Klein, Timothy P. Hogan, and Susan S. Woods, "VA OpenNotes: exploring the experiences of early patient adopters with access to clinical notes," *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association*. (2014): amiajnl-2014.

Neuner, Joan Megan Fedders, Mary Caravella, Lisa Bradford, and Marilyn Schapira. "Meaningful Use and the Patient Portal Patient Enrollment, Use, and Satisfaction With Patient Portals at a Later-Adopting Center." *American Journal of Medical Quality* 30, no. 2 (2015): 105-113.

Osborn, Chandra Y., Lindsay Satterwhite Mayberry, Shelagh A. Mulvaney, and Rachel Hess. "Patient web portals to improve diabetes outcomes: a systematic review." *Current diabetes reports* 10, no. 6 (2010): 422-435.

Otte-Trojel, Terese, Thomas G. Rundall, Antoinette de Bont, Joris van de Klundert, and Mary E. Reed. "The organizational dynamics enabling patient portal impacts upon organizational performance and patient health: a qualitative study of Kaiser Permanente," *BMC health services research* 15, no. 1 (2015): 1.

Padwal, Raj, Finlay Aleck McAlister, Peter William Wood, Pierre Boulanger, Miriam Fradette, Scott Klarenbach, Alun L. Edwards et al. "Telemonitoring and Protocolized Case Management for Hypertensive Community-Dwelling Seniors With Diabetes: Protocol of the TECHNOMED Randomized Controlled Trial." *JMIR Research Protocols*. 5, no. 2 (2016).
change: telehealth and personal health records." *Medical Care*. 49 (2011): S36-S42.

- Popeski, Naomi, Caitlin McKeen, Bushra Khokhar, Alun Edwards, William A. Ghali, Peter Sargious, Debbie White, Marilynne Hebert, and Doreen M. Rabi. "Perceived barriers to and facilitators of patient-to-provider e-mail in the management of diabetes care." *Canadian journal of diabetes* 39, no. 6 (2015): 478-483.
- Prestigiacommo, Jennifer. "Patient Portals Can Produce Real Savings." *HealthCare Informatics*. Last modified April 1, 2011., <http://www.healthcare-informatics.com/blogs/jprestigiacommo/patient-portals-can-produce-real-savings>.
- Privacy Act. RSC 1985. c P-21. <http://canlii.ca/t/52qlc>. Retrieved on 2016-06-16.
- Ralston, James D., Irl B. Hirsch, James Hoath, Mary Mullen, Allen Cheadle, and Harold I. Goldberg. "Web-based collaborative care for type 2 diabetes a pilot randomized Trial." *Diabetes care* 32, no. 2 (2009): 234-239.
- Redling, Robert. "Personal Health Record Usage And Medical Practices." *Physicianspractice.Com*. Last updated October 5, 2012. <http://www.physicianspractice.com/personal-health-records/personal-health-record-usage-and-medical-practices>
- Rehman, Jalees. "Accuracy Of Medical Information On The Internet." *Scientific American*. Last updated August 2, 2012. <http://blogs.scientificamerican.com/guest-blog/accuracy-of-medical-information-on-the-internet/>.
- Riippa, Iiris, Miika Linna, and Ilona Rönkkö. "A Patient Portal with Electronic Messaging: Controlled Before-and-After Study." *Journal of medical Internet research*. 17, no. 11 (2015).
- Sarkar, Urmimala, Andrew J. Karter, Jennifer Y. Liu, Nancy E. Adler, Robert Nguyen, Andrea Lopez, and Dean Schillinger. "The literacy divide: health literacy and the use of an internet-based patient portal in an integrated health system—results from the Diabetes Study of Northern California (DISTANCE)." *Journal of health communication*. 15, no. S2 (2010): 183-196.
- Sidani, Souraya, Mary van Soeren, Christina Hurlock-Chorostecki, Scott Reeves, Mary Fox, and Laura Collins. "Health professionals' and patients' perceptions of patient-centered care: a comparison." *European Journal for Person Centered Healthcare*. (2016).
- Silow-Carroll, Sharon, Jennifer N. Edwards, and Diana Rodin. "Using electronic health records to improve quality and efficiency: the experiences of leading hospitals." *Issue Brief (Commonw Fund)*. 17 (2012): 1-40.

- Sinnema, Jodie. "Electronic Health Record System Will Cost Hundreds of Millions, But is Vital, Government Official Says." *Edmonton Journal*. Last updated Feb 4, 2016.
<http://edmontonjournal.com/news/politics/electronic-health-record-system-will-cost-hundreds-of-million-but-is-vital-government-official-says>.
- Son, Jai-Yeol and Sung S. Kim. "Internet users' information privacy-protective responses: A taxonomy and a nomological model." *MIS quarterly* (2008): 503-529.
- Spil, Ton and Richard Klein. "Personal Health Records Success: Why Google Health Failed and What Does that Mean for Microsoft HealthVault?" In *2014 47th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences*. (2014). 2818-2827.
- Strasbourg, Dan. "Electronic Medical Records Deliver Efficiencies, Patient Safety, Improved Communication." *infoway-inforoute.ca*. Last updated April 22, 2013,
<https://www.infoway-inforoute.ca/en/what-we-do/news-events/newsroom/2013-news-releases/859-electronic-medical-records-deliver-efficiencies-patient-safety-improved-communication>
- Stylus Consulting. "Nova Scotia Personal Health Record Demonstration Project: Benefits Evaluation Report," *infoway-inforoute.ca*. (2014). Accessed May 13, 2016,
<https://www.infoway-inforoute.ca/en/component/edocman/resources/reports/benefits-evaluation/1995-nova-scotia-personal-health-record-demonstration-project-benefits-evaluation-report>.
- Tang, Paul C., Joan S. Ash, David W. Bates, J. Marc Overhage, and Daniel Z. Sands, "Personal health records: definitions, benefits, and strategies for overcoming barriers to adoption." *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association* 13, no. 2 (2006): 121-126.
- Tharmalingam, Sukirtha, Simon Hagens, and Jennifer Zelmer. "The value of connected health information: perceptions of electronic health record users in Canada." *BMC Medical Informatics and Decision Making*. 16, no. 1 (2016): 1.
- Turley, Marianne, Catherine Porter, Terhilda Garrido, Kathy Gerwig, Scott Young, Linda Radler, and Ruth Shaber. "Use of electronic health records can improve the health care industry's environmental footprint." *Health affairs* 30, no. 5 (2011): 938-946.
- Urowitz, Sara, David Wiljer, Emma Apatu, Gunther Eysenbach, Claudette DeLenardo, Tamara Harth, Howard Pai, and Kevin J. Leonard. "Is Canada ready for patient accessible electronic health records? A national scan," *BMC medical informatics and decision making* 8, no. 1 (2008): 1.
- Uslu, Aykut M. and Jürgen Stausberg. "Value of the electronic patient record: an analysis of the literature." *Journal of biomedical informatics*. 41, no. 4 (2008): 675-682.

- van Os-Medendorp, Harmieke, Hendrik Koffijberg, P. C. M. Eland-de Kok, A. van der Zalm, M. S. de Bruin-Weller, S. G. M. A. Pasmans, W. J. G. Ros, H. B. Thio, M. J. Knol, and C. A. F. M. Buijnzeel-Koomen. "E-health in caring for patients with atopic dermatitis: A randomized controlled cost-effectiveness study of internet-guided monitoring and online self-management training." *British Journal of Dermatology*. 166, no. 5 (2012): 1060-1068.
- Vogel, Lauren. "'Blue button' access to medical records." *Canadian Medical Association Journal* 182, no. 16 (2010): E746-E746.
- Warren, May. "Hospital Workers Convicted For Snooping Into Rob Ford'S Personal Health Files." *Thestar.Com*. Last updated May 6, 2016.
<https://www.thestar.com/news/gta/2016/05/06/hospital-workers-convicted-for-snooping-into-rob-fords-personal-health-files.html>.
- Weingart, Saul N., Alexander Carbo, Anjala Tess, Laurel Chiappetta, Sherri Tutkus, Laurinda Morway, Maria Toth, Roger B. Davis, Russell S. Phillips, and David W. Bates. "Using a patient internet portal to prevent adverse drug events: a randomized, controlled trial." *Journal of patient safety* 9, no. 3 (2013): 169-175
- Whetstone, Melinda, and Ronald Goldsmith. "Factors influencing intention to use personal health records." *International Journal of Pharmaceutical and Healthcare Marketing*. 3, no. 1 (2009): 8-25.
- Whiddett, Dick, Inga Hunter, Barry McDonald, Tony Norris, and John Waldon. "Consent and widespread access to personal health information for the delivery of care: a large scale telephone survey of consumers' attitudes using vignettes in New Zealand. *BMJ open* 6, no. 8 (2016): e011640.
- White W. Ryen and Eric Horvitz. "Cyberchondria: studies of the escalation of medical concerns in web search." *ACM Transactions on Information Systems. (TOIS)* 27. No. 4 (2009): 23.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1145/1629096.1629101>.
- Whitfield, Lyn. "Final death knell for HealthSpace." *digitalhealth.net*. Last updated May 22, 2012. <http://www.digitalhealth.net/news/27670/final-death-knell-for-healthspace>.
- Zelmer, Jennifer, Elettra Ronchi, Hannele Hyppönen, Francisco Lupiáñez-Villanueva, Cristiano Codagnone, Christian Nøhr, Ursula Huebner, Anne Fazzalari, and Julia Adler-Milstein. "International health IT benchmarking: learning from cross-country Comparisons." *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association*. (2016): ocw111.